

Averaging curves under the dynamic time warping distance

Koen van Greevenbroek

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Advisor: Prof. Dr. Anne Driemel

Second Advisor: Prof. Dr. Stephan Held

MATHEMATISCHES INSTITUT

MATHEMATISCH-NATURWISSENSCHAFTLICHE FAKULTÄT DER
RHEINISCHEN FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITÄT BONN

Abstract

The average curve problem under the dynamic time warping distance plays an important role in analysing and clustering time series data, with applications ranging from biology and speech recognition to finances and energy. Despite substantial effort, however, the problem resists satisfactory solutions. Recent fundamental research on the average curve problem has given us a better understanding of the difficulties involved; NP-hardness was shown in 2019. We strengthen this further by proving that there is no polynomial time constant factor approximation algorithm unless $P = NP$. On the constructive side, we focus on the problem of finding constant length average curves. Using techniques from real algebraic geometry, we present the first polynomial time algorithm for this problem. We also give a more general $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm with a better time complexity than the exact algorithm.

Keywords: Average curve problem, dynamic time warping, DTW, 1-Median, NP-hardness, time series, clustering.

MSC: Primary 62M10; Secondary 68Q25, 62H30.

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1 Introduction

In areas ranging from biology and speech recognition to finances and energy, time series data needs to be compared and classified. In geographic information systems, ordered sequences of points on a map present similar problems. In these applications, the *dynamic time warping (DTW)* distance is one of the most used distances between sequences. Briefly, given two sequences \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} of length m over a metric space (X, d) , the DTW distance between them is given by

$$\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \min_{W \in \mathcal{W}_{m,m}} \sum_{(i,j) \in W} d(a_i, b_j),$$

where $\mathcal{W}_{m,m}$ is the set of all sequences $(1, 1) = (i_1, j_1), \dots, (i_N, j_N) = (m, m)$ such that the i s and j s each increase independently by either 0 or 1 at each step. In the below example, the DTW distance between the two curves is the sum of the dotted line segments:

One of the most common tasks performed on time series data is classification using, for instance, a nearest neighbour search. Another frequently used technique is clustering of time series, all under the DTW distance. For these applications, it may be useful or necessary to find *average sequences*, also called *average curves*. An average curve looks like this (the bold red curve in the middle):

In the language of combinatorial optimisation, the average curve problem is a type of 1-MEDIAN problem; given a set \mathcal{S} of n sequences (the three thin blue curve in the above drawing), we want to find a centre curve \mathbf{c} minimising the cost

$$\phi(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \text{DTW}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}).$$

Since its inception in the 1970s, the average curve problem (which we call the DTW 1-MEDIAN problem) has proven to be notoriously hard to work with. Designing heuristics is difficult, and none of the many proposed solutions have any provable approximation guarantees.

Recently, a wave of fundamental research has shed new light on the problem. While previously implicitly assumed, NP-hardness of DTW 1-MEDIAN was finally proven in 2019. Around the same time, the first exponential time exact

algorithm was presented, based on dynamic programming. This has also been accompanied by a more rigorous study of existing heuristics. However, the current state of research still leaves open a number of questions related to the theoretical complexity of DTW 1-MEDIAN. Are there any constant factor approximation algorithms? Can anything be said about the complexity of the average curve problem for constant length curve? Are there better algorithms for more restricted versions of the DTW distance? What about curves over small alphabets?

In this paper, we significantly advance our understanding of the average curve problem on some of these fronts. First, we prove that DTW 1-MEDIAN cannot be approximated to within any constant factor unless $P = NP$ (Theorem 2, page 19), justifying the historical lack of heuristics with provable bounds. Next, we present a novel exact algorithm which runs in polynomial time for constant length centre curves (Theorem 4, page 25). The algorithm is based on partitioning the search space of centre curves, and has a geometric flavour. It shows in particular that DTW 1-MEDIAN can also be solved in polynomial time when the input curves have constant length. However, the time complexity of this algorithm is doubly exponential in the length of the centre curve, making it of little use in practice. As an alternative, we also give a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm which runs in polynomial time for constant length centre curves (Theorem 8, page 49); while essentially being a brute-force approach, it shows that more realistic runtimes may be possible. Whereas the exact algorithm works over $X = \mathbb{R}^D$, the approximation scheme has the additional advantage of being applicable in a more general context of underlying spaces X with bounded doubling dimension.

The new results are framed by an accessible introduction to the dynamic time warping distance and the average curve problem, focussing on the theoretical aspects and complexity theory in particular. We also include a complete presentation of the existing exact dynamic programming algorithm, and a discussion of DBA, the most popular heuristic for DTW 1-MEDIAN.

1.1 Related literature

Historically, the DTW distance first gained popularity in the speech recognition community, and was introduced independently around 1970 in [VZ70] and [SC71]. One of the earliest uses of the average curve problem was in time series clustering for speech recognition [RW79; WR85], which is also where the aforementioned DBA heuristic was first used. This heuristic has been rediscovered and repopularised in later years by [PKG11], and iteratively refines a centre curve in a way reminiscent of the k -means clustering algorithm. Recent improvements such as [Mor+18; LZZ19; JFS19] are in turn based on DBA. Different heuristics for the average curve problem, using hierarchical clustering techniques, include the NLAFF [Gup+96] and PSA [NR09] methods. See [SJ18] for a more in-depth review of different strategies for average curve heuristics, and [Bri+19] for an

empirical comparison of various state-of-the-art heuristics.

Whereas the above heuristics focus on applications, very little fundamental work was done on DTW 1-MEDIAN until quite recently. NP-hardness was proven independently in two separate papers [BFN19; BDS20], using different techniques. Meanwhile, [Bri+19] introduced the first exponential time exact algorithm, based on dynamical programming, with which it was possible to compare heuristics to optimum solutions on small instances. The structure of optimum centre curves has been studied in [JS20], and optimum warping paths in [JS18]. In addition to introducing a new heuristic, [SJ18] also analyses the DBA heuristic as a gradient descent method.

In the context of dynamic time warping, research on the average curve problem is dwarfed by work on time series classification: a classical problem in data science and currently the most important use case of the DTW distance. The body of literature on time series classification is vast, but for a recent survey see for example [Bag+17]. The UCR Time Series Classification Archive [Dau+18] is worth mentioning: it is the standard data archive on which most classification algorithms are evaluated. The average curve problem has uses in time series classification, see for example [Pet+14]. However, classification is beyond the scope of this text, and we focus on the average curve problem.

1.2 Organisation

The two sections following this one consist of background on the DTW distance (Section 2) and the DTW k -MEDIAN problem (Section 3). The first new result, the non-approximability of DTW 1-MEDIAN, is given in Section 4. Having established that there are no efficient exact algorithms, in Section 5 we look at exponential time exact algorithms and the structure of optimum solutions. In particular, we present our new exact algorithm in Section 5.3, while Section 5.4 gives a presentation of the dynamic programming algorithm from [Bri+19]. We move on to approximation algorithms in Section 6, including the $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation for constant length centre curves. Finally, we discuss the DBA heuristic in Section 7.

The appendices include some background reference material and some tangentially related topics. We give a brief overview of the general k -MEDIAN problem in Appendix A. As an additional reference, we give some basic definitions from complexity theory in Appendix B. Appendix C covers a linear programming formulation of DISCRETE DTW k -MEDIAN. Finally, Appendix D defines additional variations of the DTW distance which are of independent interest.

2 Dynamic time warping distance

Our main objects of interest are ordered finite sequences of points in a metric space (X, d) , such as the sequence $(0, -\frac{1}{2}, 3, 1)$ over \mathbb{R} . We call such sequences *polygonal curves*, *piece-wise linear curves* or, in this text, simply *curves* over (X, d) . We also call the points in such sequences *vertices*, and the number of vertices on a curve is its *length* or *complexity*. The following curve over \mathbb{R}^2 has length (complexity) 6:

It is worth repeating that the *length* of this sequence, as we define it, has nothing to do with the lengths of the line segments we used to draw it.

Often, we also work over an underlying space (X, d^p) for some $p \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, where the p th power means $d^p(x, y) = d(x, y)^p$. In these cases, (X, d) must still be a metric space. We specify this whenever it is applicable.

The set of curves of length m over X is simply X^m , and we let $\mathcal{V}_X = \bigcup_{m \geq 1} X^m$ denote the space of all curves over X . We always write curve $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ in bold face, while the vertices of a curve \mathbf{a} are denoted $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_m)$.

We would like a notion of distance in \mathcal{V}_X , that is, a function $D : \mathcal{V}_X \times \mathcal{V}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ satisfying at least that $D(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = D(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})$ and that $D(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$ for all $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$. We would only need the triangle inequality and that $D(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0 \implies \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$ for D to be a metric, but it turns out that this is too much to ask for in our case.

One distance that is commonly used between sets of points in a metric space is the *Hausdorff distance* d_H : for finite subsets $A, B \subseteq X$ we define

$$D_H(A, B) = \max \left\{ \max_{a \in A} \min_{b \in B} d(a, b), \max_{b \in B} \min_{a \in A} d(a, b) \right\}.$$

However, for our purposes the Hausdorff distance is not quite what we want: we would like a notion of distance that takes the ordering of our sequences into account.

Of course, for curves \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} of the same length m , we can simply sum the distances between corresponding points:

$$D_{\text{naïve}}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \sum_{i=1}^m d(a_i, b_i). \quad (1)$$

Here is an example of what this distance might look like:

The naïve distance between these two curves is the sum of the length of the dotted line segments. In the literature, this is also called the *Euclidean distance* between two curves.

However, for our purposes, we want a notion of distance that conforms more closely to our intuition of how close curves “look”: the above two curves should be close to each other. Moreover, we want a distance function on all of \mathcal{V}_X , not just between curves of the same complexity.

The distance we are looking for is called the *dynamic time warping (DTW)* distance, first seen in the speech recognition community around 1970 in [VZ70] and [SC71]. The DTW distance between the same two curves is illustrated below (it is again the sum of the lengths of the dotted line segments):

The intuition behind the DTW distance is that we jump along the points of each curve with variable “speed” and match them up as we go. Then the distance between two curves is the minimum cost of such an alignment across all possible ways of traversing the curves.

Definition 1. A *warping path* from $(1, 1)$ to (m_1, m_2) is a sequence

$$(1, 1) = (i_1, j_1), (i_2, j_2), \dots, (i_M, j_M) = (m_1, m_2)$$

such that $i_k - i_{k-1}$ and $j_k - j_{k-1}$ are either 0 or 1 for all k . Let \mathcal{W}_{m_1, m_2} be the set of all warping paths from $(1, 1)$ to (m_1, m_2) . For curves $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ of complexities m_1 and m_2 respectively, we also write $\mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}} = \mathcal{W}_{m_1, m_2}$, and call elements of $\mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}$ warping paths *between* \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . The *dynamic time warping* distance between the curves \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is

$$\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \min_{W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}} \sum_{(i, j) \in W} d(a_i, b_j). \quad (2)$$

Any warping path attaining the above minimum is called an *optimum warping path* between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} .

A few observations regarding warping paths are in order. One important property worth emphasising is the requirement for i_1, \dots, i_M and j_1, \dots, j_M to be *non-decreasing*. This is the part of the definition which takes into account that curves are *ordered* sequences; see Figure 1 for an example of what difference it can make. Indeed, the non-decreasing nature of the components of the warping paths can be made explicit in Definition 1a.

Example 1. Working over \mathbb{R} , let $\mathbf{a} = (-1, 0, 1, 0)$ and $\mathbf{b} = (0, 2, 1, 0)$. Then an optimum warping path between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is

$$W = (1, 1), (2, 1), (3, 2), (3, 3), (4, 4),$$

and the distance between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= d(a_1, b_1) + d(a_2, b_1) + d(a_3, b_2) + d(a_3, b_3) + d(a_4, b_4) \\ &= d(-1, 0) + d(0, 0) + d(1, 2) + d(1, 1) + d(0, 0) \\ &= 1 + 0 + 1 + 0 + 0 = 2. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1a. A *warping path* from $(1, 1)$ to (m_1, m_2) is a sequence $(1, 1) = (i_1, j_1), (i_2, j_2), \dots, (i_M, j_M) = (m_1, m_2)$ such that the i_1, \dots, i_M s and j_1, \dots, j_M s are non-decreasing, and that each number between 1 and m_1 and 1 and m_2 appears as some i_k and $j_{k'}$, respectively.

There is one more equivalent definition which gives a difference perspective on warping paths, using a lattice path formulation.

Definition 1b. A *warping path* from $(1, 1)$ to (m_1, m_2) is an integer lattice path from $(1, 1)$ to (m_1, m_2) using only the steps $(0, 0)$, $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$.

It is straight-forward to show that the sequence of coordinates of such a lattice path is exactly a warping path as in Definition 1, and vice versa. Because of the visual nature of lattice paths, warping paths are often illustrated in this form. See Figure 2a for three example of warping paths from $(1, 1)$ to (m, m) (here with $m = 9$), drawn as integer lattice paths.

Note that Definition 1 allows repeated terms in warping paths; they correspond to the trivial step $(0, 0)$ in Definition 1b. These repetitions are redundant: they can always be removed from warping paths without increasing the cost. Therefore, we assume without loss of generality that no warping paths have such

Figure 1: Above, the DTW distance between two curves. Below, an alignment between the points of two curves which does *not* arise from a warping path.

Figure 2: Warping paths

redundancies. A nice consequence is that the length of any warping path is between m and $2m$.

There is one more slightly less obvious redundancy which we also want to avoid. In the terminology of Definition 1b, the sequences of steps $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$ and $(1, 0)$, $(0, 1)$ can each be replaced by the single step $(1, 1)$ without increasing the cost. Therefore, we also assume without loss of generality that no warping path contains these two patterns. The warping paths in Figure 2 do not contain these patterns, which in lattice paths would look like right-angled corners.

Remark (Visual language in this paper). Most existing literature on the DTW distance deals with sequences of real number, i.e. where $X = \mathbb{R}$. Consequently, figures like the one below are often used to illustrate warping paths between sequences:

However, in this paper we prefer sequences over $X = \mathbb{R}^2$ for illustration purposes, such as in Figure 1. The reason is, perhaps counter-intuitively, that it is easier to visually inspect the DTW distance between curves over \mathbb{R}^2 than over \mathbb{R} . Specifically, when we draw a warping path between curves over \mathbb{R}^2 , as in Figure 1, the DTW distance is *actually* the sum of the lengths of the line segments representing the warping path (the dotted line segments). However, in the above plot of sequences over \mathbb{R} , this is not the case. Instead, the DTW

distance results from the differences between the x -coordinates of matched points. The fact that we “stretch” such plots along the time dimension t makes them somewhat misleading in comparison to drawings of curves over \mathbb{R}^2 .

2.1 Computing the DTW distance

Though there are exponentially many warping paths between $(1, 1)$ and (m_1, m_2) , we can use a dynamic program to compute the DTW distance between $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ of length m_1 and m_2 in $\mathcal{O}(m_1 m_2)$. We set $D(1, 1) = d(a_1, b_1)$, and for all $1 \leq i \leq m_1$ and $1 \leq j \leq m_2$ we set

$$D(i, j) = d(a_i, b_j) + \min \begin{cases} D(i-1, j) & i > 1 \\ D(i-1, j-1) & i > 1, j > 1 \\ D(i, j-1) & j > 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Then $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = D(m_1, m_2)$. The three clauses in the above minimum correspond directly to the steps $(1, 0)$, $(1, 1)$ and $(0, 1)$ in the lattice path definition of warping paths.

Example 2. Let us take the curves $\mathbf{a} = (-1, 0, 1, 0)$ and $\mathbf{b} = (0, 2, 1, 0)$ from Example 1. In the tables below we show all the pairwise distances d between the vertices of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} (left), and the array D (right):

d	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	D	1	2	3	4
b_1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	2	2
b_2	3	2	1	2	2	4	3	2	4
b_3	2	1	0	1	3	6	4	2	3
b_4	1	0	1	0	4	7	4	3	2

From the bottom right entry in the array D , we see that $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 2$. Indeed, we can think of $D(i, j)$ as the cost of a shortest path from the $(1, 1)$ th to the (i, j) th cell in the pairwise distance matrix (left), using only the three allowed steps as in Definition 1b. This shortest path is shown below, and of course corresponds to an optimum warping path between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} .

d	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
b_1	1	0	1	0
b_2	3	2	1	2
b_3	2	1	0	1
b_4	1	0	1	0

Since its first introduction, the DTW distance has been computed with the above dynamic program. A long standing open question has been whether there are any algorithms with a strictly better runtime. Finally, the first sub-quadratic

algorithm was found in 2017 [GS17], with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}\left(m^2 \frac{\log \log \log m}{\log \log m}\right)$ for curves of length m . However, it has also been shown that the DTW distance cannot be computed in strong sub-quadratic time (i.e. in $\mathcal{O}(m^{2-\epsilon})$ time) unless the Exponential Time Hypothesis (ETH) fails [BK15].

If we are willing to settle for an approximation instead of an exact computation, we can do better. Recently it was shown that an $\mathcal{O}(m^\epsilon)$ -approximation can be computed in $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(m^{2-\epsilon})$ time [Kus19]. (The $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ -notation means that factors of $\log^k m$ are ignored.) This result followed from an algorithm computing $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ in time $\mathcal{O}(m \cdot \text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}))$ under certain conditions.

If we assume that \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} satisfy some nice properties, we can get a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation [Yin+16] in linear time. In particular, the *spread* of a point set is the ratio of the maximum to the minimum pairwise distance, and a curve is called κ -packed if the length of its intersection with any ball of radius r is at most $r\kappa$. The approximation algorithm in [Yin+16] runs in $\mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} m \kappa^2 \log \sigma\right)$ time for κ -packed curves of length m with spread at most σ .

In practice, there are methods which can speed up computation of the DTW distance for most instances without giving strict runtime guarantees; see for example [ACT09]. For longer curves, exact computation of the DTW distance becomes infeasible, and approximation heuristics are usually employed instead. For example, [SC07] introduced a popular heuristic based on computing preliminary alignments between progressively downsampled time series.

Depending on the application, other techniques may be used to great effect to reduce computational time. For example, one of the most common tasks involving the DTW distance is a nearest neighbour search over a large set of time series, used to classify the query series. In this case, simple lower bounds on DTW distance can be used to reject most candidates that are far away from the query series. Lower bounds are particularly effective for the restricted w -DTW distance (see Section 2.2.2), and in practice often let the search run in linear time instead of quadratic [KPC01; KR05]. See [Bag+17] for a review of the numerous recent advances in time series classification.

2.2 Variations of the DTW distance

There are several variations of the DTW distance, both generalisations and restrictions. Specific variations are used in practice either because they are easier to work with, or because they fit specific use-cases better. In this paper, we only sometimes use a generalisation called the DTW_p^q distance, defined below. Two other popular variations are included to provide context.

2.2.1 The DTW_p^q distance

Inspired by the Euclidean distance (or any L_p -metric), it is common to raise the summands of the DTW distance to some power, and then take a root of the whole sum. This is facilitated by the following definition.

Definition 2. For any integers $p, q \geq 1$ and for any $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ we define

$$\text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \min_{W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}} \left(\sum_{(i, j) \in W} d(a_i, b_j)^p \right)^{\frac{q}{p}}.$$

The DTW_p^q distance is sometimes also denoted as the (p, q) -DTW distance. Note that the DTW_1^1 distance is simply the DTW distance as we know it from Definition 1. Apart from the DTW distance, the DTW_2^1 and DTW_2^2 distances are particularly popular in applications.

A number of results in this paper are stated over (X, d^p) for some metric space (X, d) . With the above definition, the DTW distance over (X, d^p) is just the DTW_p^p distance over (X, d) .

Note that we can easily modify the dynamic program from Section 2.1 to compute the DTW_p^q distance instead.

2.2.2 The w -DTW distance

Often, we simplify the DTW distance by restricting the family $\mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}$ of warping paths. For example, we might want to eliminate “extreme” warping paths such as $(1, 1), (1, 2), \dots, (1, m-1), (2, m), (3, m), \dots, (m-1, m), (m, m)$, with the presumption that they are unlikely to be optimum warping paths in practice. Restricting to a smaller set of warping paths can speed up both the computation of the DTW distance, and other algorithms using the DTW distance.

One common strategy is to restrict warping paths to lay within a band around the diagonal. This technique was introduced together with the original definition of the DTW distance in [SC71].

Definition 3. Let $\mathcal{W}_{m_1, m_2}^{(w)}$ be the set of warping paths between $(1, 1)$ and (m_1, m_2) for which each point (i_k, j_k) satisfies $\left| i_k - \frac{m_1}{m_2} j_k \right| \leq w$. The w -DTW distance (and indeed the w - DTW_p^q distance) is defined as the DTW distance but with $\mathcal{W}_{m_1, m_2}^{(w)}$ instead of \mathcal{W}_{m_1, m_2} .

See Figure 2b for an illustration of the warping band. In the case of $m_1 = m_2$, if we set $w = 0$ we just get the naïve distance $D_{\text{naïve}}$ as in Equation (1).

Again, the dynamic program in Section 2.1 can easily be modified to compute the w -DTW distance. Indeed, $D(i, j)$ only needs to be computed for i and j satisfying $\left| i - \frac{m_1}{m_2} j \right| \leq w$. This reduces the runtime of the dynamic program to

Figure 3: An illustration of various local patterns for restricted warping paths.

$\mathcal{O}((m_1 + m_2)w)$, which makes the w -DTW distance attractive in applications where “extreme” warping paths are unlikely to be optimal.

Another commonly used restriction, similar to the band around the diagonal as in the w -DTW distance, is the so-called Itakura parallelogram [Ita75].

2.2.3 The locally restricted DTW distance

We can also take a more local approach to restricting warping paths. The idea is to introduce certain slope constraints on warping paths (in the integer lattice path formulation), as explained for example in [SC78]. Although there are several ways of doing this, one of the easiest to implement is to restrict warping paths to only using a limited number of jumps.

For example, we can modify Definition 1b to allow only integer lattice paths using the following pattern of steps:

$$(1, 1) \text{ or } (0, 1), (1, 1) \text{ or } (1, 0), (1, 1), \quad (4)$$

instead of any combination of the steps $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$. In this example, it would be equivalent to forbid the patterns $(0, 1), (0, 1)$ and $(1, 0), (1, 0)$ in the lattice path. With this restriction, the slope of the warping path is between $1/2$ and 2 .

Of course, depending on the application we could choose more or less restrictive sets of allowed patterns. See Figure 3 for an illustration of various sets of allowed patterns. The first drawing from the left shows that original three allowed steps $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$ from Definition 1b. The second drawing shows the allowed patterns from Equation (4). Meanwhile, the third and fourth drawings show sets of patterns restricting the slope of the warping path between $2/3$ and $3/2$, and between $1/3$ and 3 , respectively.

2.3 Relation to the Fréchet distance

The DTW distance is similar to the *discrete Fréchet distance*, which for $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ is defined as

$$\min_{W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}} \max_{(i, j) \in W} d(a_i, b_j),$$

the only difference with the DTW distance being that we have replaced the summation with a maximum. The discrete Fréchet distance is also computed like the DTW distance; the only difference being that we let $D(i, j)$ be the maximum of the two terms on the right hand side of Equation (3) instead of the sum [EM94].

Informally, we could regard the DTW distance as being more tolerant of local difference between curves (“outliers”), while a small Fréchet distance gives a more uniform guarantee on how close two curves are. Thus, whether the DTW distance or the discrete Fréchet distance is more appropriate depends on the particular application. In practice, the data science community seems to prefer the DTW distance, while the Fréchet distance is used more often in the context of computational geometry.

In contrast to the DTW distance, the Fréchet distance satisfies the triangle inequality, which sometimes makes it significantly easier to work with than the DTW distance.

2.4 Non-metric properties

The DTW distance is *not* a metric. The first metric property that the DTW distance does not satisfy is the identity of indiscernibles: there are curves $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ with $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$. For example, $\text{DTW}((0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 1)) = 0$. If we want a distance function like DTW but satisfying the identity of indiscernibles, we can use the so-called *time warping invariant* distance (see Appendix D.1) instead. The second metric property that the DTW distance does not satisfy is the triangle inequality.

Example 3. The three sequences below violate the triangle inequality by a factor m :

Here, $0^{(m)}$ means m repetitions of 0.

As opposed to the identity of indiscernibles, there seems to be no easy way of constructing a distance similar to DTW which satisfies the triangle inequality. However, we can prove that the DTW distance satisfies a relaxed form of the triangle inequality which we define below.

Definition 4. Let (X, d) be a set X with a distance function d . Then d satisfies the δ -relaxed triangle inequality if for all $x, y, z \in X$ it holds that

$$d(x, z) \leq \delta \cdot (d(x, y) + d(y, z)).$$

Proposition 1. The DTW distance on curves of length at most m over a metric space (X, d) satisfies the m -relaxed triangle inequality.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ be curves of length at most m , and let $W_1 \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}$ and $W_2 \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}}$ be optimum warping paths. We explicitly construct a warping path $W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}}$ showing the m -relaxed triangle inequality between \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} , i.e. that

$$\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \leq m \cdot (\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + \text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})).$$

We construct the warping path W between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{c} by inserting a few terms for each vertex b_j of \mathbf{b} .

Let $(i, j), (i + 1, j), \dots, (i', j) \in W_1$ be the terms in W_1 whose second component is j , so that $a_i, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{i'}$ are the vertices of \mathbf{a} who are matched to $b_j \in \mathbf{b}$ by the warping path W_1 . Likewise, let $(j, k), (j, k + 1), \dots, (j, k') \in W_2$ be the terms in W_2 whose first component is j . If $i' - i \geq k' - k$, then we add to W the terms

$$W^{(j)} = \{(i, k), (i + 1, k + 1), \dots, (i + (k' - k), k'), (i + (k' - k) + 1, k'), \dots, (i', k')\}.$$

Similarly, if $i' - i < k' - k$, then we add to W the terms

$$W^{(j)} = \{(i, k), (i + 1, k + 1), \dots, (i', k + (i' - i)), (i', k + (i' - i) + 1), \dots, (i', k')\}.$$

Here is an illustration of the first case, where W_1 and W_2 are shown with thin dotted lines and W is shown with bold dotted lines:

Adding the above terms to W for each $b_j \in \mathbf{b}$ makes W a warping path between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{c} . Below is a drawing of what W may look like.

Note that in general W may contain repeated terms; this is technically allowed by the definition of warping paths, and is not a problem. It remains to show that W gives the desired bound on $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})$. First of all, we can write

$$\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \leq \sum_{(i^*, k^*) \in W} d(a_{i^*}, c_{k^*}) = \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathbf{b}|} \sum_{(i^*, k^*) \in W(j)} d(a_{i^*}, c_{k^*}). \quad (5)$$

Then each term $d(a_{i^*}, c_{k^*})$ can be bounded using the triangle inequality in X :

$$d(a_{i^*}, c_{k^*}) \leq d(a_{i^*}, b_j) + d(b_j, c_{k^*}).$$

One application of the triangle inequality has been highlighted in the previous drawing.

Now, the two distances on the right hand side are summands in $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ and $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$ respectively. Thus, we almost have a bound on $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})$ in terms of $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + \text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$. The only thing to be careful about, is that when we apply the triangle inequality in X to every term in Equation (5), each resulting distance from W_1 and W_2 may be repeated up to m times. This repetition happens when some vertex $b_j \in \mathbf{b}$ is matched to few vertices of \mathbf{a} but many vertices of \mathbf{c} (or vice versa). In the first drawing in the proof, for example, the distance $d(b_j, c_{k'})$ has to be used in three different triangle inequalities when bounding $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})$.

Because the terms in $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ and $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$ can get repeated up to m times when bounding $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})$ as in Equation (5), we get an m -relaxed triangle inequality for the DTW distance:

$$\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \leq m \cdot (\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + \text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})). \quad \square$$

Proposition 1 does not generalise in an obvious way to the DTW_p^q distance, since the distance $d^p = d(x, y)^p$ in X is not metric in general for $p > 1$. The w -DTW also does not satisfy any δ -relaxed triangle inequality.

Example 4. The following three curves violate any δ -relaxed triangle inequality under the 1-DTW distance.

The same curves also show that the locally restricted DTW distance using, for example, the step patterns in Equation (4), does not satisfy any δ -relaxed triangle inequality.

3 The DTW k -MEDIAN problem

We finally turn our attention to the average curve problem. Fundamentally, given a set of input curves, the problem is to find a single centre curve which resembles the input curves as closely as possible. Although there has not always been a consensus on how to approach this problem precisely, it has become clear that a formulation as an optimisation problem is the most fruitful. This has for example been discussed in [JS20].

In the context of optimisation problems, the average curve problem can be seen as a special case of the 1-MEDIAN problem. Broadly speaking, 1-MEDIAN asks for a centre object minimising the sum of the distances to the input objects. Instead of limiting ourselves to a 1-MEDIAN problem, we may as well consider the general k -MEDIAN problem.

DTW k -MEDIAN

Instance: A set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{V}_X$ of curves of length m .

Task: Find a set $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{V}_X$ of k curves of length m that minimises the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{C}} \text{DTW}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}).$$

We always let $n = |\mathcal{S}|$ denote the number of input curves. See Figure 4 for an example of an instance with $n = 4$ input sequences and with $k = 2$.

The case of $k = 1$ is by far the most commonly considered, and in this case we write $\phi(\mathbf{c}) = \phi(\{\mathbf{c}\})$. The DTW 1-MEDIAN problem is more or less the average curve problem as found in the rest of the literature on this topic. One variation which is often encountered is to allow the centre curve(s) \mathcal{C} to have any length instead of restricting them to the length m . We call this version the UNRESTRICTED DTW k -MEDIAN problem instead. The difference is usually not very consequential. In this paper, however, solutions \mathcal{C} to DTW k -MEDIAN must consist of centre curves of the same length as the input curves.

Figure 4: An instance \mathcal{S} (in blue) of DTW 2-MEDIAN, together with an optimum solution \mathcal{C} consisting of 2 centre curves (in bold red). The cost $\phi(\mathcal{C})$ is the sum of the dotted line segments, which indicate warping paths.

DTW k -MEDIAN can be compared to other versions of the k -MEDIAN problem, and we refer to Appendix A for a general overview over k -MEDIAN. Briefly, most variations of k -MEDIAN are NP-hard and sometimes hard to approximate within some constant factor. This always depends on the particular space over which we consider the problem. An important special case is the 1-MEDIAN problem which, in contrast to DTW 1-MEDIAN, can be computed or approximated well over discrete metric spaces or over \mathbb{R}^{ν} . See Appendix A.2.1 for more precise results.

The nature and complexity of DTW k -MEDIAN also depends on the underlying space (X, d) over which \mathcal{V}_X is defined. The case of $X = \mathbb{R}^{\nu}$, or indeed $X = \mathbb{R}$, and d the Euclidean distance are by far the most commonly considered. The squared Euclidean distance is also popular. However, DTW k -MEDIAN is well-defined (in the sense that optimum solutions exist) whenever optimum 1-medians exist in (X, d) . We work in this generality wherever possible. Recall that an optimum 1-median of a finite set $A \subseteq X$ is any point $x \in X$ minimising the cost $\sum_{a \in A} d(a, x)$.

In most algorithms for DTW k -MEDIAN, it is necessary to compute (optimum) 1-medians in the underlying space (X, d) . When $X = \mathbb{R}$, a 1-median is a median in statistical sense. Over $X = \mathbb{R}^{\nu}$ with the squared Euclidean distance, 1-medians are coordinate-wise averages. With respect to the regular Euclidean distance, however, 1-medians cannot be computed exactly in $X = \mathbb{R}^{\nu}$, only approximated. This is why most existing literature has focussed on DTW 1-MEDIAN over the squared Euclidean distance. See Appendix A.2.1 for more details.

Of course, the average curve problem can also be stated using any variation of the DTW distance such as DTW_p^q or w -DTW. We specify this where necessary. Another variation of interest is where we restrict the complexity of the centres:

DTW (k, ℓ) -MEDIAN

Instance: A set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{V}_X$ of curves of length m .

Task: Find a set $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{V}_X$ of k curves of length ℓ that minimises the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{C}} \text{DTW}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}).$$

This problem was introduced in the context of the Fréchet distance in [DKS15] as a way to reduce computational complexity; it is typical to let ℓ be much smaller than m . Letting $\ell < m$ may also prevent overfitting, actually improving the “quality” of centre curves in some cases.

However, it was noted in [DKS15] that the DTW distance may not always be the best choice between curves of very different lengths: distances such as the continuous Fréchet distance should be considered in these contexts. Thus one should be aware of the application before making ℓ much smaller than m .

A final note on the assumption that all input curves have length m : we make this assumption for convenience, but the algorithms in this paper are easily adapted to the case where not all the curves in \mathcal{S} have the same length. If we let m be the length of the longest curve in \mathcal{S} , the same complexity bounds hold.

4 Hardness and non-approximability

As opposed to many other variations of k -MEDIAN (see Appendix A), the DTW k -MEDIAN problem is NP-hard even for constant k . In particular, for hardness results we can focus on DTW 1-MEDIAN. This problem has until recently been assumed to be NP-hard more or less implicitly. It has been compared with the STEINER STRING and MULTIPLE SEQUENCE ALIGNMENT problems (which are equivalent), but no reductions have been shown. See Section 3 in [Bri+19] for an overview of some problematic statements in the literature. Only in 2019 have formal proofs of the NP-hardness of DTW 1-MEDIAN been given:

Theorem 1 ([BFN19; BDS20]). *DTW 1-MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} with the DTW_p^q distance (for any integers $p, q \geq 1$) is NP-hard, and $W[1]$ -hard with the number of input curves n as a parameter. Furthermore, DTW 1-MEDIAN cannot be solved in $\mathcal{O}(\rho(n) \cdot m^{o(n)})$ time for any computable function ρ unless the ETH fails. Here, m and n are the length and number of input curves, respectively.*

See Appendix B for some background on the parametrised complexity class $W[1]$ and the Exponential Time Hypothesis (ETH). Essentially, $W[1]$ -hardness with respect to the parameter n means that DTW 1-MEDIAN presumably cannot be solved in $\mathcal{O}(\rho(n) \cdot m^{o(1)})$ for any computable function ρ . In other words, DTW 1-MEDIAN is presumably not fixed-parameter tractable (in FPT) with n as a parameter. Of course, the last statement in the theorem is a strengthening of this, dependent on the ETH. The notation $o(n)$ (“little-o notation”) denotes functions which, informally speaking, have a strictly slower asymptotic growth than n .

In fact, this result has been proven (in the case of the DTW_2^2 distance) even for binary input sequences [BFN19]. The proof in [BDS20] uses input sequences over three values instead of two, but holds with respect to the DTW_p^q distance for any integers $p, q \geq 1$. These two cited articles actually work with UNRESTRICTED DTW 1-MEDIAN (where the centre curve can have any length), but we can easily reduce to DTW 1-MEDIAN using the fact that in the unrestricted case, there is always an optimum centre curve of length at most mn [JS20]. Therefore, we can solve UNRESTRICTED DTW 1-MEDIAN using an algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN by finding optimum centre curves of every length $1, 2, \dots, mn$. It follows that if UNRESTRICTED DTW 1-MEDIAN is NP-hard, then so is DTW 1-MEDIAN.

4.1 Hardness of approximation of DTW 1-MEDIAN

As we have seen that DTW 1-MEDIAN is NP-hard, the question remains how hard the problem is to approximate. Already from [BDS20] it follows that there cannot exist a polynomial time approximation scheme for DTW 1-MEDIAN. Furthermore, the first version of the same paper [BDS19] mentioned that the NP-hardness proof can also be adapted to show that there is no constant factor

approximation algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN (with ℓ part of the input) unless $P = NP$.

We show that DTW 1-MEDIAN has no constant factor approximation algorithm (unless $P = NP$), answering a question posed in [BDS20]. In fact, DTW 1-MEDIAN cannot even be approximated within a logarithmic factor (unless $P = NP$).

Theorem 2. *There does not exist any constant factor approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} unless $P = NP$. Furthermore, there exists some $\delta > 0$ such that if there is a $(\log n)^\delta$ -approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} , then $NP \subseteq QP$. All of the above holds with respect to the DTW_p^q distance for any integers $p, q \geq 1$.*

Here, QP denote the class of problems solvable in *quasi-polynomial* time, i.e. in $\mathcal{O}(2^{(\log n)^c})$ for some $c > 0$. The ETH implies that $NP \not\subseteq QP$. In other words, the theorem implies that it is unlikely for there to be an algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN with an approximation ratio better than logarithmic.

To prove this theorem, we use a reduction from the following problem:

SHORTEST COMMON SUPERSEQUENCE (SCS)

Instance: A set \mathcal{S} of strings over a finite alphabet Σ .

Task: Find the shortest string $w \in \Sigma^*$ such that every $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is a subsequence of w .

Here, we say that s is a *subsequence* of w if there are indices $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_m$ such that $s = w_{i_1} w_{i_2} \dots w_{i_m}$.

The above problem is not to be confused with the related problem SHORTEST COMMON SUPERSTRING, where we look for the shortest w such that each $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is a *substring* of w , that is, w can be written $w = asb$ for some $a, b \in \Sigma^*$. Note also that (in contrast to DTW k -MEDIAN), the input strings to SCS are not required to all be of the same length.

SCS was proven NP-complete in the late 70s [Mai78], and shortly after, it was shown that it even remains NP-complete over a binary alphabet [RU81]. There was a long search for approximation algorithms for SCS, but more than a decade later Jiang and Li finally proved the following result:

Theorem 3 ([JL95]). *There does not exist any constant factor approximation algorithm for SCS unless $P = NP$. Furthermore, there exists some $\delta > 0$ such that if there is $(\log n)^\delta$ -approximation algorithm for SCS (where $n = |\mathcal{S}|$), then $NP \subseteq QP$.*

Note, however, that the above theorem has not been proven for the special case of SCS over binary sequences, as is the case for the NP-hardness of SCS.

We actually need Theorem 3 to also hold for SCS restricted to instances where all the inputs strings have the same length.

Lemma 1. *Let UNIFORM SCS be the SHORTEST COMMON SUPERSEQUENCE problem where all input strings in \mathcal{S} have the same length M . Then the non-approximation results from Theorem 3 hold for UNIFORM SCS as well as for SCS.*

Proof. Suppose there is an α -approximation algorithm for UNIFORM SCS. Let \mathcal{S} be an instance of SCS over the alphabet Σ , and let M be the maximum length of any string in \mathcal{S} . Define the instance \mathcal{S}' of UNIFORM SCS in terms of \mathcal{S} by appending enough copies of some symbol $X \notin \Sigma$ to each string $s \in \mathcal{S}$ to make all the strings of length M . Let t and t' be the lengths of shortest common supersequences for \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{S}' respectively, and note that $t' \leq t + M$. So an α -approximation algorithm for UNIFORM SCS yields a superstring of length at most $\alpha \cdot (t + M) \leq 2\alpha \cdot t$ (noting that $M \leq t$), giving a 2α -approximation for SCS. \square

The authors of [JL95] mention that the $(\log n)^\delta$ -factor in Theorem 3 might possibly be improved to n^δ . If true, this implies that there is no algorithm with an approximation factor better than *polynomial* in n unless $\text{NP} \subseteq \text{QP}$, both for SCS and for DTW 1-MEDIAN.

The proof of Theorem 2 is inspired by the reduction of SCS to DTW 1-MEDIAN from [BDS20]. For clarity, some of the details are put in three claims which are proven independently. Directly following the complete proof is a worked example of the reduction on a small instance with $p = q = 1$.

Proof of Theorem 2. Suppose that there exists an α -approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} for some $\alpha \geq 1$. We show that this gives an β -approximation algorithm for UNIFORM SCS with $\beta = 2^p \alpha^{p/q}$: then letting α be constant and letting $\alpha = (\log n)^\delta$ give the two parts of the theorem.

Let \mathcal{S} be an instance of UNIFORM SCS over the alphabet Σ , with strings of length M . Let t^* be the length of a shortest common supersequence of \mathcal{S} . Furthermore, write $n = |\mathcal{S}|$, and $r = |\Sigma|$.

We define an instance \mathcal{S}' of DTW 1-MEDIAN by constructing for each $s \in \mathcal{S}$ a corresponding sequence $\theta(s) \in \mathcal{S}'$ over \mathbb{R} . First, let $\pi : \Sigma \rightarrow \{r + 1, r + 2, \dots, 2r\}$ be a bijection, which we use to map letters of s to vertices (real numbers) of the curve $\theta(s)$, and back. For a later bound, we need the numbers $\pi(\Sigma)$ to be far enough away from 0; hence the “offset” by r .

Now, let $x^{(K)} = x, x, \dots, x$ denote the sequence consisting of K repetitions of x , and for $s = s_1 s_2 \dots s_M \in \mathcal{S}$, define the following sequence over \mathbb{R} :

$$\theta(s) = 0^{(K)}, \pi(s_1)^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, \pi(s_2)^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, \dots, 0^{(K)}, \pi(s_M)^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}.$$

Here, K is to be determined later, but is polynomial in n, M and r . In particular, $|\theta(s)| = (2M + 1)K$ is polynomial in the size of the instance \mathcal{S} .

Let OPT be the optimum value of the DTW 1-MEDIAN instance \mathcal{S}' , and use the α -approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN to obtain a 1-median curve \mathbf{c} of cost $\phi(\mathbf{c}) \leq \alpha \cdot \text{OPT}$. Also fix optimum warping paths between \mathbf{c} and each $\theta(s) \in \mathcal{S}'$. We use \mathbf{c} to construct a common supersequence w for \mathcal{S} of length at most $\beta \cdot t^*$, so that w is a β -approximation. The strategy of can be illustrated as follows:

To construct the supersequence w from \mathbf{c} , we loosely follow the terminology of [BDS20] and call $x \in \mathbf{c}$ a *signal vertex* if it is within a distance of $1/3$ from any number in $\pi(\Sigma)$. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t be the signal vertices in \mathbf{c} (in the same order as in \mathbf{c}), and let nint be the nearest integer function. Then we define

$$w = \psi(\mathbf{c}) = \pi^{-1}(\text{nint}(x_1)), \pi^{-1}(\text{nint}(x_2)), \dots, \pi^{-1}(\text{nint}(x_t)).$$

By definition w is a string over Σ . We want to show that w is a common supersequence for \mathcal{S} . For this, we need a good upper bound on OPT in terms of t^* , the length of a shortest common supersequence.

Claim 1. $\text{OPT} \leq n(2r)^q(t^* - M)^{\frac{q}{p}}$.

Using this bound, we can show that w is a common supersequence for \mathcal{S} when we make K sufficiently large.

Claim 2. Let $K = \lceil Mn(6r)^p(\alpha n)^{p/q} \rceil$. Then w is a common supersequence for \mathcal{S} .

It remains to show that w is a β -approximation: we need to bound the length t of w . In particular, we can bound t from above using $\phi(\mathbf{c})$.

Claim 3. $nr^q(t - M)^{\frac{q}{p}} \leq \phi(\mathbf{c})$.

Using this bound together with $\phi(\mathbf{c}) \leq \alpha \cdot \text{OPT}$ and Claim 1, we get the desired approximation guarantee.

$$\begin{aligned} nr^q(t - M)^{\frac{q}{p}} &\leq \phi(\mathbf{c}) \leq \alpha \cdot n(2r)^q(t^* - M)^{\frac{q}{p}} \\ t - M &\leq 2^p \alpha^{\frac{p}{q}} (t^* - M) \\ t &\leq \beta \cdot t^*. \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Claim 1. Let w^* be a shortest common sequence of \mathcal{S} of length t^* . To prove the bound on OPT, we use w^* to construct a centre curve \mathbf{c}' for \mathcal{S}' of cost at most $n(2r)^q(t - M)^{q/p}$. Namely, take

$$\mathbf{c}' = 0, \pi(w_1^*), 0, \pi(w_2^*), 0, \dots, 0, \pi(w_{t^*}^*), 0, 0, \dots, 0$$

with enough trailing zeros so that $|\mathbf{c}'| = (2M + 1)K$. To bound the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c}') = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}', \theta(s))$, we examine $\text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}', \theta(s))$ for each $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Since s is a subsequence of w^* , each block $\pi(s_d)^{(K)}$ of $\theta(s)$ can be matched to a distinct corresponding vertex of \mathbf{c}' . There remain $t^* - M$ non-zero vertices of \mathbf{c}' that are not matched: they have to be matched to zeros in $\theta(s)$ and cost at most $(2r)^p$ each. Of course, all zeros in \mathbf{c}' can be matched exactly with zeros in $\theta(s)$, and vice versa. The result is a warping path between \mathbf{c}' and $\theta(s)$, and so

$$\text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}', \theta(s)) \leq ((2r)^p(t^* - M))^{\frac{q}{p}} = (2r)^q(t^* - M)^{\frac{q}{p}}.$$

Since $|\mathcal{S}| = n$ we conclude that $\text{OPT} \leq \phi(\mathbf{c}') \leq n(2r)^q(t^* - M)^{q/p}$. \square

Proof of Claim 2. To show that w is a common supersequence for \mathcal{S} , we show that w is a supersequence of s for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Following the definition, we have to find for $s \in \mathcal{S}$ a sequence of indices $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_M$ such that $s = w_{i_1}w_{i_2} \dots w_{i_M}$. We use an optimum warping path between \mathbf{c} and $\theta(s)$ to find these indices.

First, it is important that there is some signal vertex on \mathbf{c} for each vertex $\pi(s_i)$ on $\theta(s)$. Otherwise, the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c})$ would be too high. Indeed, consider the distance $\text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}, \theta(s))$. When \mathbf{c} has no signal vertex for $\pi(s_i)$, then all K vertices in the block $\pi(s_i)^{(K)}$ of $\theta(s)$ would have to be matched to some vertex on \mathbf{c} further than $1/3$ away, and we would have

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{c}) &\geq \text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}, \theta(s)) \geq \left(K \frac{1}{3p}\right)^{\frac{q}{p}} \\ &= \left([Mn(6r)^p(\alpha n)^{p/q}] \frac{1}{3p}\right)^{\frac{q}{p}} > (t^* - M)^{\frac{q}{p}}(2r)^q(\alpha n) \geq \alpha \cdot \text{OPT}, \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

contradicting that \mathbf{c} is an α -approximation. Here, we used that $t^* - M < t^* \leq Mn$, and the last inequality holds by Claim 1.

Now that we know that there is a signal vertex on \mathbf{c} for each non-zero vertex on $\theta(s)$, we can define the indices i_1, \dots, i_M showing that s is a subsequence of w . Fix an optimum warping path between \mathbf{c} and $\theta(s)$, and let x be any vertex of \mathbf{c} matched to (a part of) the block $\pi(s_j)^{(K)}$ of $\theta(s)$. As we have just shown, x is a signal vertex for $\pi(s_j)$, so by definition of $w = \psi(\mathbf{c})$ we have that $\pi^{-1}(\text{nint}(x))$ is a letter in w . Let i_j be the index of this letter in w .

Note that since x is a signal vertex for $\pi(s_j)$ (so $|x - \pi(s_j)| \leq 1/3$), we have that $s_j = w_{i_j}$. So indeed $s = w_{i_1}w_{i_2} \dots w_{i_M}$. It remains to show that $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_M$.

The indices of warping paths are non-decreasing; therefore $i_1 \leq i_2 \leq \dots \leq i_M$. Finally, suppose for a contradiction that $i_j = i_{j+1}$ for some j . Then a single vertex x of \mathbf{c} (corresponding to the i_j letter in w) is matched to vertices in both blocks $\pi(s_j)^{(K)}$ and $\pi(s_{j+1})^{(K)}$ of $\theta(s)$. But then x must also be matched by the warping path to the entire block of zeros $0^{(K)}$ between the two blocks $\pi(s_j)^{(K)}$ and $\pi(s_{j+1})^{(K)}$. Be a similar calculation as in Equation (6), this would imply that $\phi(\mathbf{c}) > \alpha \cdot \text{OPT}$, a contradiction. \square

Proof of Claim 3. To prove that $nr^q(t - M)^{\frac{q}{p}} \leq \phi(\mathbf{c})$, we use that \mathbf{c} contains t signal vertices, but the curves in \mathcal{S}' contain only $M \leq t$ blocks of signal vertices. By an argument similar to the one in proof of Claim 1, we see that for each $\theta(s)$ there are $t - M$ vertices on \mathbf{c} that cannot be matched to vertices on $\theta(s)$ exactly, and cost at least r^p each. Therefore, $\text{DTW}_p^q(\mathbf{c}, \theta(s)) \geq (r^p(t - M))^{q/p}$, and hence $\phi(\mathbf{c}) \geq nr^q(t - M)^{q/p}$. \square

By setting $\alpha = 1$, the above proof also yields another proof of the NP-hardness of DTW 1-MEDIAN, which is arguably simpler than that in either [BDS20] or [BFN19]. If we only want to show NP-hardness, we can reduce from SCS on the binary alphabet, which is still NP-hard. Modifying π to map the binary alphabet to $\{-1, 1\}$ instead of $\{3, 4\}$ simplifies the proof, and eliminates the factor of 2^p in the approximation ratio β . Then an exact algorithm (i.e. with $\alpha = 1$) for DTW 1-MEDIAN yields an exact algorithm for SCS. This shows the NP-hardness of DTW 1-MEDIAN over sequences with 3 distinct points (like the proof from [BDS20]), as opposed to the stronger result from [BFN19] for binary sequences.

Example 5. Consider the SCS instance $\mathcal{S} = \{x, y, z\}$ over the alphabet $\Sigma = \{A, B, C\}$ given by

$$x = \text{ABAC}, \quad y = \text{CBAB}, \quad z = \text{ABBC}.$$

We use an α -approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN (with respect to DTW_1^1 , i.e. with $p = q = 1$) to construct a common supersequence for x , y and z of length at most 2α the optimum length. Let us set $\alpha = 2$, so that in this example, $K = 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 6 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 = 1296$. To construct our instance \mathcal{S}' of DTW 1-MEDIAN, we first need a bijection $\pi : \{A, B, C\} \rightarrow \{4, 5, 6\}$; we take $\pi(A) = 4$, $\pi(B) = 5$ and $\pi(C) = 6$. Then \mathcal{S}' consists of the curves

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(x) &= 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 6^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, \\ \theta(y) &= 0^{(K)}, 6^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, \\ \theta(z) &= 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 6^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}. \end{aligned}$$

Using our hypothetical 2-approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN on

\mathcal{S}' , suppose we get a centre curve

$$\mathbf{c} = 0, 4, 0, 6, 0, 5, 0, 4, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0, 6, 0, 0, \dots, 0.$$

The signal vertices of \mathbf{c} (those close to numbers in $\pi(\Sigma)$) are 4, 6, 5, 4, 4, 5, 6, so \mathbf{c} induces the sequence $w = \text{ACBAABC}$ over Σ , of length $t = 7$. Indeed, w is a common supersequence of x , y and z :

$$\begin{array}{lll} x: & A & BA & C \\ w: & ACBAABC & & \\ y: & CB & AB & \\ w: & ACBAABC & & \\ z: & A & B & BC \\ w: & ACBAABC & & \end{array}$$

Of course, we choose K large enough to guarantee that w is a common supersequence of \mathcal{S} . (See Claim 2.)

Now, we show that w is a 4-approximation. Suppose that t^* is the length of a shortest common supersequence; we want to show that $|w| = t \leq 4t^*$.

We start by examining the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c})$ of \mathbf{c} . An optimum warping path between $\theta(x)$ and \mathbf{c} , for example, could look like this:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \theta(x) : & 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 5^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 4^{(K)}, 0^{(K)}, 6^{(K)}, 0^{(K)} \\ \mathbf{c}' : & 0, 4, 0, 6, 0, 5, 0, 4, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0, 6, 0, 0, \dots, 0 \end{array}$$

Here, the only parts of the warping path that cost anything are the three solid lines: we see that $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{c}, \theta(x)) = 6 + 4 + 5 = 15$. In fact, optimum warping paths between \mathbf{c} and the other two curves $\theta(y)$ and $\theta(z)$ look very similar: because \mathbf{c} has $t = 7$ signal vertices while the curves in \mathcal{S}' have 4 blocks of signal vertices, the DTW distance is always going to be the sum of $t - 4 = 3$ non-zero differences. In particular, $\phi(\mathbf{c}) \geq n \cdot r \cdot (t - 4) = 9 \cdot (t - 4)$. (See Claim 3.)

On the other hand, we can use the length of a shortest common supersequence for \mathcal{S} to bound $\phi(\mathbf{c})$ from above. Suppose that w^* is a shortest common supersequence for \mathcal{S} of length t^* . As in the proof, we can use w^* to construct a centre curve \mathbf{c}' for \mathcal{S} , with t^* signal vertices. Much in the same way as above, we can bound the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c}')$, but this time from above. The DTW distance between \mathbf{c}' and any curve in \mathcal{S}' is the sum of only $t^* - 4$ non-zero differences (represented by the solid edges in the previous illustration), and each of these difference can be at most $2r = 6$. So $\phi(\mathbf{c}') \leq n \cdot 2r \cdot (t^* - 4) = 18 \cdot (t^* - 4)$. (See Claim 1.)

Finally, we use that \mathbf{c} is a 2-approximation: this means that $\phi(\mathbf{c}) \leq 2 \cdot \text{OPT} \leq 2 \cdot \phi(\mathbf{c}') \leq 36 \cdot (t^* - 4)$. Putting everything together, we have

$$9 \cdot (t - 4) \leq \phi(\mathbf{c}) \leq 36 \cdot (t^* - 4) \implies t \leq 4t^*.$$

5 Exact algorithms

As shown in Section 4, the DTW 1-MEDIAN problem is NP-hard (even to approximate), putting polynomial time exact algorithms out of reach. However, we can still investigate exact algorithms for special cases, or exponential time exact algorithms. We are particularly interested in the complexity of DTW 1-MEDIAN, parametrised in either the number n or length m of the input curves, or the length ℓ of the centre curve. The main focus of this section is a new exact algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN which runs in polynomial time when ℓ is constant.

The only exact algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN in the literature to this date (to the author's knowledge) is a dynamic program given in [Bri+19]. Its time complexity is roughly of the form $\mathcal{O}(m^{2n})$, meaning that it runs in polynomial time when the number of input curves n is constant. In the language of parametrised complexity we say that DTW 1-MEDIAN is in XP with n as a parameter.¹ The dynamic program was also used to empirically evaluate the performance of several heuristics relative to optimum solutions on small instances. We present it in Section 5.4, including a small modification improving the runtime slightly.

A natural question remains: are there algorithms which run in polynomial time when some *other* parameter is constant? Both [Bri+19] and [BFN19] asked whether an average curve can be found in polynomial time when the length of the input curves is constant. After developing the necessary theory in Sections 5.1 to 5.2, we answer the question in the affirmative with the following theorem (in Section 5.3):

Theorem 4. *The DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN problem over $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the squared Euclidean distance can be solved in $\mathcal{O}((mn)^{f(\ell, \nu)})$ time for some function f , when ℓ is constant. Here, m and n are the length and number of input curves, respectively.*

Our result is stronger than what [Bri+19] and [BFN19] asked for: we only require a constant length centre curve for polynomial runtime. The runtime of this algorithm shows that DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN is in XP with ℓ as a parameter, and hence that DTW 1-MEDIAN is in XP with m as a parameter. The algorithm can also be made to work with the L_1 -metric on \mathbb{R}^ν .

The function f in the runtime is exponential in ℓ and ν , making the runtime of the whole algorithm doubly exponential in ℓ . This means our algorithm is of limited practical value. Moreover, it is still an open question whether DTW 1-MEDIAN might be fixed-parameter tractable with the length of the curves m as a parameter; for this we would need an algorithm with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}(\rho(m) \cdot n^{\mathcal{O}(1)})$ for some computable function ρ . It should be noted that DTW 1-MEDIAN cannot (presumably) be fixed-parameter tractable with the number

¹A parametrised problem is in XP exactly if it can be solved in polynomial time when the parameter is constant. See Appendix B for a brief introduction to parametrised complexity.

of curves n as a parameter by Theorem 1, so fixed-parameter tractability is only open with respect to m (and ℓ in case of DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN).

At first glance, it may seem difficult to search for centre curves over an infinite space such as \mathbb{R}^v . Fortunately, optimum centre curves have a certain discrete structure we can exploit. In order to make full use of this structure, we give a number of definitions in the following section. Before getting started, we give a motivational example to show the direction.

Example 6. Consider a set of input curves \mathcal{S} and an optimum centre curve \mathbf{c} as on the left side of this drawing:

In this case, $m = 4$ and $\ell = 3$. On the right side, we have drawn in an optimum warping path between each $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$ and the centre curve \mathbf{c} . Then, we have indicated for each $x \in \mathbf{c}$ the points S_x it is matched to on the input curves.

A fundamental observation is that when \mathbf{c} is optimum, then $x \in \mathbf{c}$ has to be an optimum 1-median in X of the points in S_x . In other words, x has to minimise the sum of the distances to the points in S_x . We see this in the drawing: x sits “in the middle” of S_x . (In this drawing, we actually use the squared Euclidean distance.)

It follows that $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$ is “encoded” by the sets S_{c_1} , S_{c_2} and S_{c_3} . This makes optimum centre curves discrete objects in some sense.

We can also go in the other direction: the sets $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, S_2, S_3)$ define a curve $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ where the i th point is a 1-median of S_i . See the following drawing:

This suggests a naïve but working algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN: simply try $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ for all possible $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_\ell)$. At least one of the resulting curves has to be an optimum centre curve.

The example is lacking in rigour. What can the collections of sets \mathbf{S} look like? How exactly are they related to warping paths? After having laid a solid foundation with these concepts, we can use them for more efficient exact algorithms.

A final remark about the DTW (k, ℓ) -MEDIAN problem before we delve into definitions. Although we deal with the DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN problem in this section, any algorithm for this problem can be used as a subroutine for DTW (k, ℓ) -MEDIAN by simply guessing the k clusters. With this brute-force approach, there are $\mathcal{O}(k^n)$ ways of partitioning \mathcal{S} into k clusters. Thus, the DTW (k, ℓ) -MEDIAN problem can be solved in polynomial time when n is constant, using the dynamic program from Section 5.4 as a subroutine to find the centre curves of each cluster.

5.1 Warping paths and sections

The fundamental discrete objects when it comes to understanding optimum centre curves are of course warping paths. Given an instance \mathcal{S} of DTW 1-MEDIAN, we consider a collection of warping paths, one for each $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$. We also introduce an important equivalent way of specifying such collections using what we call *sections* of the input curves, focussing on which points on the input curves each point on a centre curve is matched to. Intuitive maps between collections of warping paths, collections of sections and centre curves form powerful tools in the design of exact algorithms.

The following definitions all depend on a fixed set of input curves $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ of length m . The length of centre curves ℓ is also fixed. Since we are interested in centre curves of length ℓ , we work with the warping paths $\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}$.

Definition 5. Fix integers $m, \ell \geq 1$. A *collection of warping paths* is a tuple $\mathbf{W} = (W_{\mathbf{s}} \mid \mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S})$ where $W_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}$. The set of collections of warping paths is simply $(\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$.

The second perspective uses a new object we have not seen before.

Definition 6. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves. A *section* of \mathcal{S} is a set containing for each curve $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$ a non-empty substring \mathbf{s}' of \mathbf{s} . By non-empty substring, we mean that $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{s}'\mathbf{b}$ for some sequences \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , and $|\mathbf{s}'| \geq 1$. While a section A of \mathcal{S} is a set of $|\mathcal{S}|$ curves in \mathcal{V}_X , we also sometimes abuse notation and write A to mean the set of vertices in the section A , namely $\bigcup A \subseteq X$.

A section looks like this:

In Figure 5, the sets S_1, S_2, S_3 and S_4 are also examples of sections. A set of n curves of length m has $\mathcal{O}(m^{2n})$ different sections, since each substring \mathbf{s}' is determined by its two endpoints.

Just as collections of warping paths are important, so are collections of sections.

Definition 7. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves. A *collection of sections* is a tuple $\mathbf{S} = (S_j \mid 1 \leq j \leq \ell)$, where S_j is a section of \mathcal{S} .

In practice, we always associate the j th section in a collection \mathbf{S} with the j th vertex of a centre curve. This is analogous to warping paths being associated with pairs of curves, even though they are just sequences of indices.

There is a natural map from collections of warping paths to collections of sections, which we call Ψ .

Definition 8. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m . Given $\mathbf{W} \in (\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$, let $\Psi(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{S} = (S_j \mid 1 \leq j \leq \ell)$ be defined by

$$S_j = \{s_i \mid (i, j) \in W_s, \mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}\}.$$

We call the elements of $\Psi((\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n)$ *proper collections of sections*.

In words, the j th section in $\Psi(\mathbf{W})$ consists of all vertices in \mathcal{S} which are matched to the j th point of a centre curve by the warping paths \mathbf{W} .

Example 7. Let $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$ be a set of two curves of length 4, and let $\ell = 3$. Consider the collection of warping paths $\mathbf{W} = (W_{\mathbf{a}}, W_{\mathbf{b}}) \in (\mathcal{W}_{4,3})^2$ with

$$\begin{aligned} W_{\mathbf{a}} &= ((1, 1), (2, 2), (3, 2), (4, 3)), \\ W_{\mathbf{b}} &= ((1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 3), (4, 3)). \end{aligned}$$

Then the collection of sections $\Psi(\mathbf{W}) = (S_1, S_2, S_3)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= \{(a_1), (b_1)\}, \\ S_2 &= \{(a_2, a_3), (b_1)\}, \\ S_3 &= \{(a_4), (b_2, b_3, b_4)\}. \end{aligned}$$

See Figure 5 for a visual example of $\Psi(\mathbf{W})$. Although for illustration purposes it is useful to draw a centre curve, note that $\Psi(\mathbf{W})$ only depends on the warping paths \mathbf{W} (and the fixed input curves \mathcal{S}), and not any centre curve.

It is easy to verify that Ψ is injective, so that it is a bijection between the collections of warping paths and the proper collections of sections. In this sense, proper collections of sections are just different ways of representing collections of warping paths.

What makes the collections of warping paths and sections useful is that we have natural maps between them and centre curves in X^ℓ . The most natural map is from X^ℓ to $(\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$.

Definition 9. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves. Given a curve $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$, define $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}) = (W_s \mid \mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S})$ by letting W_s be an optimum warping path between \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{c} . We call $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$ a collection of optimum warping paths between \mathcal{S} and \mathbf{c} .

Figure 5: An example of how to map a collection of warping paths to a collection of sections. Here with $n = 3$, $m = 5$ and $\ell = 4$. The three different warping paths W_{s_1} , W_{s_2} , W_{s_3} have been given different dash patterns for clarity.

The second natural map is from collections of sections to X^ℓ , and uses 1-medians in the underlying space X .

Definition 10. Let $S \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves. Given a collection of sections \mathbf{S} , define $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S}) = (c_1, \dots, c_\ell)$ by letting c_j be an optimum 1-median in X of S_j .

We have seen a preview of both maps \mathbf{W}_{opt} and $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}$ in Example 6. In particular, mapping collections of sections to centre curves looks like this:

The two maps $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$ and $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ can be composed with Ψ ; we also introduce notation for this.

Definition 11. Let $S \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m , let $\mathbf{W} \in (\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$ and let $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$. Write

$$\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\Psi(\mathbf{W})) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}) = \Psi(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})).$$

Furthermore, if x is the j th point on \mathbf{c} , let S_x denote the j th section S_j of $\mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$. We call S_x the *section (of S) aligned with x* .

A diagram of the various maps is given in Figure 6. We have already seen the notation S_x in Example 6, but see Figure 7 for another illustration.

A few remarks are worth making. First of all, neither optimum warping paths nor 1-medians need be unique in general, which means that \mathbf{W}_{opt} and $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}$ are technically not well-defined. To resolve this, we simply assume that arbitrary canonical choices are made; this is not a problem for our purposes.

Figure 6: An illustration of the various maps between collections of warping paths, collections of sections, and the centre curves X^ℓ . The maps that were defined explicitly are indicated with solid arrows, while the dashed arrows indicate induced maps from Definition 11.

Figure 7: The sections aligned with the points of a centre curves (in bold red). Note however that, contrary to what this drawing may suggest, $x \notin S_x$ for any point $x \in \mathbf{c}$; the section S_x only includes point from the input curves \mathcal{S} .

We note that for most $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$, we have $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})) \neq \mathbf{c}$ and for most $\mathbf{W} \in (\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$ we have $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})) \neq \mathbf{W}$. Indeed, note that the maps \mathbf{W}_{opt} and $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}$ (on $(\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$) are neither injective nor surjective. By the bijection Ψ , the same of course holds for sections.

Finally, note that we can write the cost of a centre curve \mathbf{c} for \mathcal{S} using the sections $\mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$:

$$\phi(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y). \quad (7)$$

Essentially, this is grouping the distances which make up the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c})$ by section, and not by warping path.

It is worth noting that Equation (7) does *not* hold with respect to the DTW_p^q distance (except with $p = q$, in which case we effectively work over (X, d^p)). With the DTW_p^q distance (Definition 2), the roots prevent us from rearranging to term of $\phi(\mathbf{c})$. This is the main reason that results in this section do not generalise to the DTW_p^q distance.

5.2 The structure of optimum centre curves

Now that we have developed some language to talk about collections of warping paths and sections, we can start to work with optimum centre curves. A simple but fundamental realisation is that optimum centre curves are determined by their warping paths to the input curves. This is the easiest to state in terms of sections.

Proposition 2. *Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m , and let $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$ be an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} . Then each $x \in \mathbf{c}$ is an optimum 1-median of S_x in X .*

Proof. Suppose for a contradiction that $x \in \mathbf{c}$ is *not* a 1-median of S_x in X , so there exists some x' such that $\sum_{y \in S_x} d(x', y) < \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y)$. Then we could replace x by x' in \mathbf{c} to get a strictly better centre curve for \mathcal{S} (noting that $\sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y)$ is a term in $\phi(\mathbf{c})$ by Equation (7)), contradicting the optimality of \mathbf{c} . \square

Though simple, this proposition is crucial for algorithm design. It gives optimum centre curves a discrete structure. Instead of struggling with the whole (possibly infinite) space X^ℓ , we only need to consider curves whose points are 1-medians of sections of \mathcal{S} .

The result was previously stated in the context of $X = \mathbb{R}$ with the squared Euclidean distance in [Bri+19]; we have just reproduced it here in our notation and in more generality. Note that Proposition 2 works over any (X, d) in which optimum 1-medians exist; the distance function d need not satisfy the triangle inequality.

We can see visually how the proposition holds on Figure 7, where the bold red curve is an optimum centre curve. In this figure, we have used the squared Euclidean distance. Note that indeed, each point x on a centre curve is a 1-median (“in the middle”) of the section S_x .

One consequence of Proposition 2 is that when \mathbf{c} is an optimum centre curve, then up to uniqueness of 1-medians in X , we have $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}))$. A way to state this fact without the ambiguity of the 1-medians in X is as follows.

Lemma 2. *Let $\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m , and let $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$ be an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} . Then $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}))$ (equal to $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c}))$ by definition) is also an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} .*

An informal way to state Lemma 2 is that if we start with an optimum centre curve in X^ℓ and go around the diagram in Figure 6 following the solid maps, we end up with an optimum centre curve again. In contrast, if we do the same procedure starting with any (non-optimum) curve in X^ℓ , we often end up with a very different curve.

We can interpret Proposition 2 as saying that, up to uniqueness of 1-medians in X , an optimum centre curve \mathbf{c} is encoded by its sections $\mathbf{S}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$. Equivalently (by Ψ), the curve \mathbf{c} is encoded by its optimum warping paths $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})$ to the input curves. This suggests two exact algorithms for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN employing an exhaustive search, one based on sections and one based on warping paths.

Lemma 3. *Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m . Then we can find an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} by either taking*

1. *The cheapest $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ over all collections of sections \mathbf{S} , or taking*
2. *The cheapest $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ over all collections of warping paths \mathbf{W} .*

Of course, the two algorithms come down to the same since they both use the map $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}$. The difference is that the first checks $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ for *all* collections of sections \mathbf{S} , while the second effectively only checks $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{S})$ for proper collections of sections $\mathbf{S} = \Psi(\mathbf{W})$.

With curves \mathcal{S} of length m , there are less than m^{2n} sections of \mathcal{S} , so the first algorithm in Lemma 3 tries out $\mathcal{O}(m^{2n\ell})$ centre curves. Meanwhile, the number of warping paths in $\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}$ is given by the Delannoy numbers $D_{m,\ell}$; one classical formula for $\ell \leq m$ is

$$|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}| = D_{m,\ell} = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{i} \binom{m}{i} 2^i. \quad (8)$$

So the second algorithm in Lemma 3 tries $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^n = (D_{m,\ell})^n$ centre curves.

As a side note, warping paths and the injectivity of Ψ show combinatorially that $D_{m,\ell} < m^{2\ell}$, although we could also verify this fact algebraically.

In any case, both algorithms have a time complexity which is exponential in both ℓ and n . We have included them here as a motivation, and to show that exact algorithms for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN exist at all. To find an algorithm whose time complexity is only exponential in ℓ requires more sophisticated ideas.

5.3 A partitioning algorithm

We can now start working on the new exact algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN which runs in polynomial time for constant ℓ . On a high level, it uses Cylindrical Algebraic Decomposition (CAD), a tool from real algebraic geometry, to partition the search space X^ℓ into a polynomial number (for constant ℓ) of regions. We design the partition of X^ℓ such that in each region $F \subseteq X^\ell$ of the partition, all curves $\mathbf{b} \in F$ have the same optimum warping paths $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$ to \mathcal{S} . To find an optimum centre curve, we then only need to check a single curve in each set of the partition.

5.3.1 Warping-invariant sets

Since it takes too long to consider all collections of warping paths, as we did in Lemma 3, we use the geometry of the space of centre curves X^ℓ to our advantage. A key idea is that we can find regions in X^ℓ where all curves have the same optimum warping paths to all the input curves.

Definition 12. Let $\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m . A set $F \subseteq X^\ell$ is called *warping-invariant (with respect to \mathcal{S})* if for any curves $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in F$, the optimum warping paths $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{a})$ between \mathcal{S} and \mathbf{a} are also optimum between \mathcal{S} and \mathbf{b} .

For example, the two centre curves \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in Figure 8 have the same unique optimum warping paths to \mathcal{S} . Therefore $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$ is warping-invariant.

Example 8. Two simple but more general examples of warping-invariance.

- (a) When $m = \ell = 2$, there is only one warping path: $((1, 1), (2, 2))$. Then all of X^ℓ is warping-invariant.
- (b) When $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$, any centre curve $\mathbf{c} \in X^m$ whose points lie sufficient far away from the input curves \mathcal{S} has the same optimum warping paths to \mathcal{S} : each warping path is the “trivial” path $(1, 1), (2, 2), \dots, (m, m)$. Therefore the entire set of curves whose points lie far away from \mathcal{S} is warping-invariant.

Warping-invariance is useful because, to find an optimum centre curve, it is sufficient to find a warping-invariant set containing an optimum centre curve.

Lemma 4. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m , and let $F \subseteq X^\ell$ be a warping-invariant set containing an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} . Then for any $\mathbf{b} \in F$, the

Figure 8: The two curves **a** and **b** have the same optimum warping paths to S . Thus $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$ is warping-invariant.

curve $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b}))$ is also an optimum centre curve for S .

Proof. Let $\mathbf{c} \in F$ be some optimum centre curve contained in F by assumption. By definition of warping-invariance, $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$ are also optimum warping paths between S and \mathbf{c} . Then $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ is an optimum centre curve for S by Lemma 2. \square

Another perspective is that we can find a (not necessarily unique) collection of warping paths \mathbf{W} for each warping-invariant set F , and thus a partition of X^ℓ into warping-invariant sets gives a set of collections \mathbf{W} . One of these collections of warping paths defines an optimum centre curve by Lemma 4. In this sense, finding a small partition of X^ℓ into warping-invariant sets gives a small corresponding set of collections of warping paths. This is in contrast to simply trying out $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ for all $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^n$ collections of warping paths, as in Lemma 3. Assuming we can find such a small partition, this essentially tells us that the vast majority of the $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^n$ possible collections of warping paths can never occur as optimum warping paths to *any* centre curve. Another way to put this is that the image of X^ℓ in $(\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell})^n$ under the map \mathbf{W}_{opt} is relatively small (of polynomial size).

Of course, it remains to find a suitable partition of X^ℓ into warping-invariant sets.

5.3.2 Partitioning the space of centre curves

More structure is needed to construct the partition; from now on we work over $X = \mathbb{R}^v$ with the squared Euclidean distance $d(x, y)^2 = \sum_{\mu=1}^v (x_\mu - y_\mu)^2$. To study warping-invariant regions, we need a notion of distance along specific warping paths.

Definition 13. For curves $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ and a warping path $W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}$, let

$$D(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}; W) = \sum_{(i,j) \in W} d(a_i, b_j)^2$$

denote the *distance between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} along W* . Note that with this notation, we can write $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \min_{W \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}} D(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}; W)$.

Distances along specific warping paths were previously considered in [JS18], in the context of proving that optimum warping paths are unique between most pairs of curves over \mathbb{R}^ν in a measure-theoretic sense. Here, we take the definition in a different direction.

We are interested in comparing the distances along different warping paths. To this end, we introduce indicator functions for pairs of warping paths and specific $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$, telling which of the two warping paths costs less between \mathbf{s} and a given $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$. Write $s_{i\mu}$ for the μ th coordinate of $s_i \in \mathbb{R}^\nu$, and similarly for \mathbf{c} . Then

$$\begin{aligned} D(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}; W) &\leq D(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}; W') \\ \sum_{(i,j) \in W} d(s_i, c_j)^2 &\leq \sum_{(i,j) \in W'} d(s_i, c_j)^2 \\ \sum_{(i,j) \in W} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} (c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu})^2 &\leq \sum_{(i,j) \in W'} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} (c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu})^2 \\ 0 &\leq Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}(\mathbf{c}) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

In other words, the sign of $Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}(\mathbf{c})$ indicates which of W and W' is the cheaper warping path between \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{c} . We choose to make \mathbf{c} the argument since we want $Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}$ to be a function over the search space X^ℓ . In fact, $Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}$ is a real polynomial in $\ell\nu$ variables. When the coordinates of the curves in \mathcal{S} are given as rational numbers, then $Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}$ has rational coefficients.

Example 9. One of the simplest examples is with $m = 3$ and $\ell = 2$, so that there are only two warping paths in $\mathcal{W}_{m, \ell}$:

$$\begin{aligned} W_1 &= ((1, 1), (2, 2), (3, 2)), \quad \text{and} \\ W_2 &= ((1, 1), (2, 1), (3, 2)). \end{aligned}$$

Work with $X = \mathbb{R}$, let $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3) \in \mathcal{S}$ and let $\mathbf{c} = (x, y)$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mathbf{a}, W_1, W_2} &= ((x - a_1)^2 + (x - a_2)^2 + (y - a_3)^2) \\ &\quad - ((x - a_1)^2 + (y - a_2)^2 + (y - a_3)^2) \\ &= (x - a_2)^2 - (y - a_2)^2. \end{aligned}$$

We can use these indicator functions to construct warping-invariant sets in X^ℓ . Let

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'} \mid \mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}, W, W' \in \mathcal{W}_{m, \ell}\} \tag{10}$$

be the set of all possible indicator functions for a given \mathcal{S} and ℓ . Note that although \mathcal{Q} depends on \mathcal{S} and ℓ , we suppress this from the notation since they are always clear from the context.

Lemma 5. Let $S \in \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m . Let $F \subseteq X^\ell$ such that the sign of every function in \mathcal{Q} is constant. Then F is warping-invariant.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in F$, and consider the collection of optimum warping paths $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{a}) = (W_s \mid \mathbf{s} \in S)$. Then $Q_{s, W_s, W}(\mathbf{a}) \geq 0$ for all $\mathbf{s} \in S$ and all $W \in \mathcal{W}_{m, \ell}$. By assumption on F , we also get that $Q_{s, W_s, W}(\mathbf{b}) \geq 0$ for all $\mathbf{s} \in S$ and all $W \in \mathcal{W}_{m, \ell}$. But then $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{a})$ are also optimum warping paths between S and \mathbf{b} , so F is warping-invariant. \square

It follows that to partition X^ℓ into warping-invariant regions, it suffices to partition X^ℓ into regions where the functions in \mathcal{Q} have constant sign.

Example 10. Let $X = \mathbb{R}$ and $\ell = 3$, and consider the following two curves of length 3:

$$\mathbf{a} = (5, 2, -1), \quad \mathbf{b} = (0, -3, 2).$$

There are three warping paths in $\mathcal{W}_{3,3}$:

$$W_1 = ((1, 1), (2, 2), (3, 3)),$$

$$W_2 = ((1, 1), (2, 1), (3, 2), (3, 3)),$$

$$W_3 = ((1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 3)).$$

All in all, we get six indicator functions:

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{Q_{\mathbf{a}, W_1, W_2}, Q_{\mathbf{a}, W_1, W_3}, Q_{\mathbf{a}, W_2, W_3}, Q_{\mathbf{b}, W_1, W_2}, Q_{\mathbf{b}, W_1, W_3}, Q_{\mathbf{b}, W_2, W_3}\}.$$

These are all real polynomials in $\ell \nu = 3$ variables. In order to create a 2-dimensional figure, consider the centre curve $\mathbf{c} = (x, y, 0)$. Below we have plotted the six curves defined by $Q(x, y, 0) = 0$ for $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$:

In this plot, each contiguous region between the curves is a warping-invariant set, because the sign of each indicator function in \mathcal{Q} is constant in these regions.

Partitioning $X^\ell = \mathbb{R}^{\ell\nu}$ into regions where the polynomials in \mathcal{Q} have constant sign can be done directly with the Cylindrical Algebraic Decomposition (CAD) algorithm. However, we first take a slight detour to study the theory of arrangements. Apart from being an interesting topic on its own right, arrangements can help us understand the structure of what we are working with.

5.3.3 Arrangements of surfaces

Arrangements are a broad topic in discrete geometry, and we only briefly cover some fundamentals here. See [Mat02] for an accessible reference on the topic.

Definition 14. The *arrangement* formed by sets $A_1, \dots, A_N \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$ is the partition of $\mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$ defined by the equivalence relation \sim where $x \sim y$ if and only if x and y belong to the same subcollection of A_i s, that is, $\{i \mid x \in A_i\} = \{i \mid y \in A_i\}$. The elements of an arrangement (the sets making up the partition of $\mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$) are called the *faces* of the arrangement.

What we call faces are sometimes called *cells* in other sources: the terminology is not entirely standardised and we follow Matoušek.

The classical examples are arrangements of hyperplanes, where the A_i s are half-spaces (for each hyperplane, the two corresponding closed half-spaces). See for instance Figure 9 for one of the simplest hyperplane arrangement: that of two straight (non-parallel) lines in \mathbb{R}^2 . However, we are interested in the arrangement of the indicator functions we saw in the previous section.

Definition 15. Let f_1, \dots, f_N be functions $f_i: \mathbb{R}^\nu \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The *arrangement of f_1, \dots, f_N* is the arrangement of the sets $Z_{\leq 0}(f_i) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^\nu \mid f(x) \leq 0\}$ and $Z_{\geq 0}(f_i) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^\nu \mid f(x) \geq 0\}$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$.

By this definition, the sign of each f_i is constant in every face of the arrangement of f_1, \dots, f_N . The signs $\{-, 0, +\}$ correspond to the possibilities of $x \in \mathbb{R}^\nu$ being just in $Z_{\leq 0}(f_i)$, in both $Z_{\leq 0}(f_i)$ and $Z_{\geq 0}(f_i)$, or just in $Z_{\geq 0}(f_i)$.

Figure 9: The arrangement of two straight lines partitions \mathbb{R}^2 into 4 regions, 4 line segments and 1 point.

Figure 10: An arrangement of four polynomials in \mathbb{R}^2 .

A priori, the number of faces in an arrangement of N functions could be up to 3^N : the number of ways of choosing a sign $\{-, 0, +\}$ for each of the N functions. Indeed, each face F in an arrangement of functions is uniquely identified by its *sign pattern*: a vector $\sigma \in \{-, 0, +\}^N$ whose i th component indicates the sign of f_i in F . However, we are in the lucky case that the indicator functions $Q_{s,W,W'}$ are polynomials, the number of faces in the arrangement of polynomials is in fact much less than 3^N .

Example 11. Figure 10 shows the arrangement of four polynomials Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 and Q_4 . For each polynomial, the positive side has been shaded, and some of the faces have been marked with their sign pattern. Note that some faces may have multiple connected components: for example the faces with sign patterns $(+, -, 0, 0)$ and $(+, -, 0, -)$ have two connected components each. Not all $3^4 = 81$ sign patterns occur in this arrangement: it has only 46 distinct faces. For instance, there is no face with the sign pattern $(-, 0, -, 0)$ in this example: Q_2 and Q_4 do not intersect on the negative side of Q_1 and Q_3 (the upper side of the drawing).

A classical result in the theory of arrangement, often called the Milnor-Thom theorem, tells us that the number of faces in the arrangement of polynomials is *not* exponential in N . The following is a modern, tight formulation.

Theorem 5 ([Mat02]). *Let Q_1, \dots, Q_N be real polynomials in ν' variables, of degree at most D . Then the number of faces in the arrangement of Q_1, \dots, Q_N is at most*

$$2(2D)^{\nu'} \sum_{i=0}^{\nu'} 2^i \binom{4N+1}{i} \leq \left(\frac{50DN}{\nu'} \right)^{\nu'},$$

where the latter bound holds for $N \geq \nu' \geq 2$.

In our case, consider the arrangement of \mathcal{Q} , with $|\mathcal{Q}| = n|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^2$. Then we have the following.

Corollary 1. *Let \mathcal{F} be the arrangement of the indicator functions \mathcal{Q} . Then*

$$|\mathcal{F}| \leq \left(\frac{100|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^2}{\ell^\nu} \cdot n \right)^{\ell\nu}.$$

In particular, $|\mathcal{F}|$ is polynomial in m and n when ℓ is constant. By the argument made at the end of Section 5.3.1, this means that in some sense, only a polynomial number (for constant ℓ) of the $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^n$ possible collections of warping paths \mathbf{W} can ever occur as collections of optimum warping paths to any centre curve $\mathbf{c} \in X^\ell$.

5.3.4 Cylindrical Algebraic Decomposition

Although we have seen that the arrangement of polynomials cannot contain exponentially many faces, computing the arrangement is a separate issue. It is strongly tied to the more fundamental problem of solving systems of real polynomial inequalities. This is a difficult problem, and only in 1975 did Collins introduce the celebrated Cylindrical Algebraic Decomposition (CAD) algorithm to solve such systems, involving complicated techniques from real algebraic geometry. See [Jir95] for an accessible introduction to the topic.

Given inequalities

$$Q_1 \geq 0 \wedge \cdots \wedge Q_N \geq 0, \quad Q_i \in \mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_{\nu'}], \quad (11)$$

the basic idea is to partition $\mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$ into regions in which each Q_i has a constant sign, and produce a sample point inside each region: this is the exact same technique we also want to use. Then, the feasibility of Equation (11) over $\mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$ is determined by evaluating Q_1, \dots, Q_N at each of the sample points.

Without going into further details, we present the CAD algorithm as a black-box result suited to our needs.

Theorem 6 ([Col75]). *Let $Q_1, \dots, Q_N \in \mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_{\nu'}]$ be polynomials of constant degree. Then we can find in $\mathcal{O}(N^{g(\nu')})$ time, for some function g , a partition of $\mathbb{R}^{\nu'}$ into sets where all Q_1, \dots, Q_N have constant sign, and produce a sample point in each set of the partition.*

Ignoring smaller order terms, the function g is of the form $2^{\nu'}$. However, see [Col75] for a more precise time complexity.

It should be noted that although the input polynomials Q_1, \dots, Q_N have rational coefficients, the sample points produced by the CAD algorithm may have real

algebraic coordinates in general. However, the problem of representing real algebraic numbers and evaluating the sign of polynomials at these points can be addressed. For a modern and self-contained reference on the topic, see for example [BPR06].

The way cylindrical algebraic decomposition works, the partition produced by the CAD algorithm in general contains many more elements than the arrangement of Q_1, \dots, Q_N as discussed in Section 5.3.3. Thus, the output of the CAD algorithm is a refinement of the arrangement of Q_1, \dots, Q_N . Either way, the CAD algorithm applied to the indicator functions \mathcal{Q} gives us a partition of X^ℓ into warping-invariant sets, allowing us to solve DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN efficiently for constant ℓ . We already stated the result at the beginning of Section 5, but restate it here:

Theorem 4. *The DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN problem over $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the squared Euclidean distance can be solved in $\mathcal{O}\left((mn)^{f(\ell, \nu)}\right)$ time for some function f , when ℓ is constant. Here, m and n are the length and number of input curves, respectively.*

We do not give a more precise runtime in order to avoid cluttering the essence of the result. In any case the function f , coming from g in Theorem 6, is itself exponential in ℓ and ν , making the full algorithm doubly exponential in ℓ .

Proof of Theorem 4. Let an instance \mathcal{S} of DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN be given. Compute the set of polynomials \mathcal{Q} as per Equation (10). By Theorem 6 (the CAD algorithm), we can compute a partition \mathcal{F} of $X^\ell = \mathbb{R}^{\ell\nu}$ into sets on which the sign of every function in \mathcal{Q} is constant, in addition to a sample point in each set of the partition. Let $F \in \mathcal{F}$ be a set in the partition containing some optimum centre curve \mathbf{c}^* for \mathcal{S} , and let $\mathbf{b} \in F$ be the sample point produced by the CAD algorithm. By Lemma 5, F is warping-invariant. So by Lemma 4, $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b}))$ is an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} . Note that we can compute $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ exactly given $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$ since we are working over $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the squared Euclidean distance.

See Figure 11 for an illustration of the face F .

As noted previously, the sample point \mathbf{b} produced by the CAD algorithm may have real algebraic coordinates. This needs to be taken into account when computing the optimum warping paths $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$. The warping paths are computed using the dynamic program in Equation (3), Section 2.1, and to this end we need to perform exact arithmetic and comparisons on real algebraic numbers. A common way to address this is to represent algebraic numbers by their minimal polynomial together with an interval with rational endpoints. With some care, we can use this representation to add, multiply and compare algebraic numbers exactly and efficiently. Indeed, this or an equivalent representation must be used by the CAD algorithm to return the sample points in the first place, including \mathbf{b} . See for example Section 8.5 in [Mis93] for a good introduction to working with

Figure 11: A conceptual illustration of the partition \mathcal{F} with a warping-invariant face F containing an optimum centre curve \mathbf{c}^* highlighted. The sample point \mathbf{b} is produced by the CAD algorithm.

real algebraic numbers.

The runtime of the algorithm is dominated by the use of the CAD algorithm to produce the partition \mathcal{F} . The number of polynomials that we run the algorithm on is $N = |\mathcal{Q}| = n \cdot |\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|^2$. Recalling the formula for $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}|$ in Equation (8), we see that $|\mathcal{W}_{m,\ell}| \in \mathcal{O}(m^\ell)$ for constant ℓ . So for constant ℓ , we have that $N \in \mathcal{O}(n \cdot m^{2\ell})$, and by Theorem 6 finding \mathcal{F} takes $\mathcal{O}((n \cdot m^{2\ell})^{g(\ell\nu)})$ time for some function g . Since computing a collection $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$ and the centre curve $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b}))$ takes polynomial time in m and n , we conclude that the total runtime of the algorithm can be written as $\mathcal{O}((mn)^{f(\ell,\nu)})$ for some f . \square

5.3.5 Extensions

Theorem 4 is stated over $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the squared Euclidean distance. Here, we show that the same result also holds with the L_1 -metric instead of the squared Euclidean distance. In particular, this means that the algorithm works over \mathbb{R} with both the usual distance $d(x, y) = |x - y|$ (the L_1 -metric) and the alternative (squared Euclidean) distance $d(x, y) = (x - y)^2$.

Given a set of input curves \mathcal{S} , we can define the indicator functions as in Equation (9) but with respect to the L_1 -metric on \mathbb{R}^ν :

$$Q_{\mathbf{s},W,W'}(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{(i,j) \in W'} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} |c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}| - \sum_{(i,j) \in W} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} |c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}|.$$

At this point, we could proceed the same way as in the proof of Theorem 4, if it were not for the fact that $Q_{\mathbf{s},W,W'}$ is no longer a polynomial due to the absolute values. The solution is to first partition X^ℓ into sets where all the terms $c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}$ have constant sign, so that the $Q_{\mathbf{s},W,W'}$ are polynomials within these regions and we can find an optimum centre curve in each region separately.

Concretely, let $Y = \{s_{i\mu} \mid 1 \leq \mu \leq \nu, 1 \leq i \leq m, \mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{S}\}$ be the set of all distinct coordinates of points on curves in \mathcal{S} . We have that $|Y| \leq \nu \cdot m \cdot n$. Now, write

$Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_{|Y|}\}$ with $y_1 < \dots < y_{|Y|}$, and let

$$\mathcal{Y} = \{(-\infty, y_1), [y_1, y_2), [y_2, y_3), \dots, [y_{|Y|}, \infty)\}$$

be the partition of \mathbb{R} induced by Y . Then we can write $\mathcal{Y}^{\ell\nu}$ for the partition of $X^\ell = \mathbb{R}^{\ell\nu}$ by cartesian products of elements of \mathcal{Y} .

For any cell $A \in \mathcal{Y}^{\ell\nu}$, the terms $c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}$ have a constant sign, so $Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}$ is a polynomial in A . Therefore, we can find an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} inside $A \in \mathcal{Y}^{\ell\nu}$ using the same argument as in the proof of Theorem 4. Repeating this for all $(\nu mn + 1)^{\ell\nu}$ elements of $\mathcal{Y}^{\ell\nu}$ gives an optimum centre for \mathcal{S} . When ℓ is constant, this is still a polynomial time algorithm. The last thing to note is that we can compute 1-medians in \mathbb{R}^ν exactly under the L_1 -metric: they are just coordinate-wise medians in the statistical sense.

In more general contexts, we can still partition X^ℓ as in the proof of Theorem 4, but $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ might not be computable exactly (for example 1-medians in \mathbb{R}^ν with the Euclidean distance cannot be computed exactly for $\nu \geq 2$, see Appendix A.1). Since we usually have good approximation algorithms for 1-MEDIAN in the underlying space X , we can still approximate $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ to any desired precision given \mathbf{W} .

For example, let d denote the L_1 -metric on \mathbb{R}^ν , and write $d^p(x, y) = d(x, y)^p$ as before. Then we can work over (\mathbb{R}^ν, d^p) by defining:

$$Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{(i,j) \in W'} \left(\sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} |c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}| \right)^p - \sum_{(i,j) \in W} \left(\sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} |c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu}| \right)^p.$$

When d is the Euclidean distance and we work over (\mathbb{R}^ν, d^p) , we get

$$Q_{\mathbf{s}, W, W'}(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{(i,j) \in W'} \left(\sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} (c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu})^2 \right)^{\frac{p}{2}} - \sum_{(i,j) \in W} \left(\sum_{\mu=1}^{\nu} (c_{j\mu} - s_{i\mu})^2 \right)^{\frac{p}{2}},$$

which is a polynomial for even p . We can make a similar definition for any $L_{p'}$ -metric on \mathbb{R}^ν . In all these cases, we can use the same argument as in the proof of Theorem 4 (and possibly using the partition $\mathcal{Y}^{\ell\nu}$) to find a partition of X^ℓ into warping-invariant sets, and hence a collection of warping paths $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{b})$ such that $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ is optimum (without necessarily being able to compute $\mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W})$ exactly).

5.4 Dynamic programming

We have seen a naïve algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN, based on trying all possible curves of all possible sections of \mathcal{S} , with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}(m^{2n\ell})$. Dynamic programming can essentially eliminate the ℓ from the above runtime. Specifically, [Bri+19] gives a dynamic programming algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN

with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}(f(mn) \cdot m^{2n+1} 2^n \ell^2 n)$, where $f(N)$ is the time it takes to compute an optimum 1-median of N points in X . A direct consequence of this dynamic program is that DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN is in XP with the number of curves as a parameter: it can be solved in polynomial time for constant n .

Here, we present a slight modification of the algorithm in [Bri+19] which eliminates the factor of 2^n from the time complexity. We also use the more general context of any underlying space (X, d) where we can compute optimum 1-medians in polynomial time (which is usually not difficult; see Appendix A.2.1). The original version was stated over \mathbb{R} with the squared Euclidean distance $d(x, y) = (x - y)^2$.

Theorem 7. *Let (X, d) be a space over which solutions to the 1-MEDIAN problem exist and can be computed in $f(N)$ time. Then DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN over X can be solved in $\mathcal{O}(f(mn) \cdot m^{2n+1} \ell^2 n)$ time. Here, m and n are the length and number of input curves, respectively.*

We do not require d to be a metric (to satisfy the triangle inequality in particular), meaning that the algorithm also works over the squared Euclidean distance, for instance. Before proving the theorem, we need a small technical lemma relating to how sections aligned with adjacent points on an optimum centre curve can interact.

Lemma 6. *Let x, y be adjacent points on an optimum centre curve \mathbf{c} of \mathcal{S} , and let S_x and S_y be the sections of \mathcal{S} aligned with x and y , respectively. Consider the restrictions $\mathbf{s}_{(x)} = S_x \cap \mathbf{s}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{(y)} = S_y \cap \mathbf{s}$ of the sections to a single curve $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$. Either $\mathbf{s}_{(x)} \cap \mathbf{s}_{(y)} = \emptyset$ and $\mathbf{s}_{(x)}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{(y)}$ are adjacent on \mathbf{s} , or $\mathbf{s}_{(x)} = \mathbf{s}_{(y)}$ and $|\mathbf{s}_{(x)}| = |\mathbf{s}_{(y)}| = 1$.*

The two possibilities in the lemma look like this:

The lemma follows directly from the definition of warping paths, and because we assume that there are no redundant patterns of the form $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$ and $(1, 0)$, $(0, 1)$ in optimum warping paths. Such a pattern would correspond to the case of $\mathbf{s}_{(x)} \cap \mathbf{s}_{(y)} \neq \emptyset$ but $\mathbf{s}_{(x)} > 1$ or $\mathbf{s}_{(y)} > 1$, which the proposition rules out.

Proof of Theorem 7. Let a set $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n\}$ of n curves of length m over X be given. We consider tuples of indices $I, J \in \{1, \dots, m\}^n$, and say that $I \leq J$ if and only if $I_i \leq J_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$. Now, let $\mathcal{S}[J]$ denote the section of \mathcal{S} resulting from truncating \mathbf{s}_i to the length J_i for each $1 \leq i \leq n$. Finally, we denote by $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$ any optimum solution to the instance $\mathcal{S}[J]$ of DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN.

That is, $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$ is a curve of length ℓ , and of course $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}, \ell) = \mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[\{m\}^n], \ell)$ is the solution we are looking for. Note that optimum centre curves are not unique, so we just look to compute *any* optimum solution.

The following claim gives a recursive construction for $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$.

Claim 4. *Let the non-empty range $(i, j]^*$ be defined as*

$$(i, j]^* = \begin{cases} \{i + 1, i + 2, \dots, j\} & \text{if } i < j \\ \{j\} & \text{if } i = j \end{cases}$$

Similarity define the non-empty range $(I, J]^$ component-wise, and define the section $\mathcal{S}(I, J]^*$ analogously to $\mathcal{S}[J]$. Then for $\ell > 1$,*

$$\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell) = \mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[I], \ell - 1) \circ \mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}(I, J]^*, 1) \quad (12)$$

for some $I \leq J$.

Here, we use \circ to denote concatenation of sequences. Of course, $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}(I, J]^*, 1)$ is just an optimum 1-median (in X) of all the points on $\mathcal{S}(I, J]^*$, computed in $\mathcal{O}(f(mn))$ time.

Clearly $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell) = \mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[I], \ell - 1) \circ (x)$ for some $I \leq J$ and some $x \in X$; to prove the claim, it remains to show that $(x) = \mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}(I, J]^*, 1)$. Equivalently, we need to show that $S_x = \mathcal{S}(I, J]^*$. Let y be the last point on $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[I], \ell - 1)$, and let S_y be the section of $\mathcal{S}[I]$ aligned with y . For each curve $\mathbf{s}_i \in \mathcal{S}$, the largest index of any point in $S_y \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ is I_i . We have two cases:

Case 1: $I_i = J_i$. Then $S_y \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ intersects $S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i$, and by Lemma 6 we have $|S_y \cap \mathbf{s}_i| = |S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i| = 1$. The single point in $S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ has index J_i .

Case 2: $I_i < J_i$. Then $S_y \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ cannot intersect $S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ because otherwise $|S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i| > 1$, which is impossible by Lemma 6. Therefore $S_y \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ and $S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ are adjacent, and $S_x \cap \mathbf{s}_i$ contains the points with indices $\{I_i + 1, \dots, J_i\}$.

Together, these cases show (on the scale of individual curves in \mathcal{S}) that $S_x = \mathcal{S}(I, J]^*$ as desired. See Figure 12 for an illustration of the two cases.

So to compute $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$, we simply take the cheapest of all the curves as in Equation (12) for $I \leq J$.

Since the number of indices $I \leq J$ is in $\mathcal{O}(m^n)$ and computing the cost of a centre curve takes $\mathcal{O}(m\ell n)$ time, computing $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$ takes $\mathcal{O}(f(mn) \cdot m^{n+1}\ell n)$ time if all previous partial centre curves have already been computed. There are $\mathcal{O}(m^n \ell)$ partial centre curves of the form $\mathbf{c}(\mathcal{S}[J], \ell)$, so the whole algorithm has a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(f(mn) \cdot m^{2n+1}\ell^2 n)$. \square

Figure 12: The section $S_x = S(I, J]^*$ aligned with the last point x on $\mathbf{c}(S[J], \ell)$, restricted to one of the input curves \mathbf{s}_i . *Case 1* is top left, while the other drawings are examples of *Case 2*.

Figure 13: An illustration of the construction of an optimum centre curve as in Theorem 7. The points in non-empty ranges of the form $S(I, J]^*$ are indicated with the shaded regions.

Example 12. See Figure 13 for an optimum centre curve constructed by the above algorithm. In this example the centre curve has the form

$$C(\mathcal{S}, 7) = C(\mathcal{S}[(7, 7, 7)], 7) = C(\mathcal{S}[(7, 6, 5)], 6) \circ C(\mathcal{S}((7, 6, 5), (7, 7, 7))^*, 1).$$

We have

$$((7, 6, 5), (7, 7, 7))^* = (\{7\}, \{7\}, \{6, 7\}),$$

so the last point on the centre curve is the 1-median of 4 points on the input curves, marked with $\mathcal{S}(I_4, I_5)^*$ in the drawing.

As in [Bri+19], we note that the dynamic program can easily be modified to find optimum solutions to UNRESTRICTED DTW 1-MEDIAN instead (where the centre curve can have any length). Essentially, in this case it is no longer required to keep track of the lengths of optimum partial solutions (so we write $C(\mathcal{S}[J])$ for an optimum partial solution), and Equation (12) becomes that

$$C(\mathcal{S}[J]) = C(\mathcal{S}[I]) \circ C(\mathcal{S}(I, J)^*, 1)$$

for some $I < J$. Note that I has to be strictly smaller (in at least one of the components) than J to avoid an infinite recursion in this case. Some additional work is required to show that optimum solutions of bounded length exist in this case; see [Bri+19] for the details.

Finally, a note about the runtime of the algorithm. It is shown in [BFN19] that optimum solutions to DTW 1-MEDIAN cannot be computed in $\mathcal{O}(m^{o(n)})$. Since the exponential factor in the runtime of this dynamic program is m^{2n+1} , it is close to optimal in some sense. A question posed in [BFN19] is whether there are exact algorithms with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}(m^n)$ or $\mathcal{O}(m^{\alpha n})$ for some small $\alpha > 1$.

6 Approximation algorithms

As we have seen in Section 4, there is no constant factor approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} . Of course, plenty of heuristics have been proposed over the years (see Section 7). However, if we want to design algorithms with provable approximation guarantees, we have to look for restricted versions of DTW 1-MEDIAN.

As in Section 5 on exact algorithms, we focus on DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN with constant ℓ once more. Of course, we already know a polynomial time algorithm for this problem (Theorem 4). However, this exact algorithm has a few drawbacks, such as its prohibitive runtime and needing techniques from real algebraic geometry. If we settle for approximation algorithms instead of exact algorithms, can we address these issues in some way?

The answer is yes. In this section, we give a fully polynomial time approximation scheme for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN with constant ℓ . This approximation scheme works over any (X, d^p) where (X, d) is a metric space with bounded doubling dimension. Moreover, the runtime of the approximation scheme is exponential in ℓ , but not *doubly* exponential in ℓ like the partitioning algorithm from Section 5. So while the approximation scheme is still not very efficient by any means, it illustrates that more computationally feasible solutions to the average curve problem may be possible.

Informally speaking, we can say that there are two difficulties with finding optimum centre curves: the length of the centre curves, and the number of possible points that centre curves can use. The length m of the centre curves for DTW k -MEDIAN makes it hard to construct solutions point by point: we easily end up with a time complexity exponential in m . As we have seen in Section 5, each point on an optimum centre curve is a 1-median of a section of the input curves, of which there are also exponentially many.

The first difficulty is eliminated by only looking for constant length centre curves. To overcome the second difficulty, we look at different discretisations of the underlying space X , so as to reduce the number of points that a centre curve can use. In the process, we have to give up some accuracy. First, we find a simple 2-approximation, and in Section 6.2 we refine this to a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation.

6.1 Discrete centre curves

The first step is to consider centre curves using only points of the input curves. We introduce this as a new optimization problem.

Figure 14: An optimum 1-median solution \mathbf{c} (left) and the corresponding “rounded” discrete 1-median solution \mathbf{c}' (right).

DISCRETE DTW k -MEDIAN

Instance: A set $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ of curves of length m .

Task: Let $P = \bigcup \mathcal{S}$ be the set of points of the sequences in \mathcal{S} . Find a set $\mathcal{C} \subseteq P^m$ of k curves of length m over P that minimises the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{C}} \text{DTW}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}).$$

We call solutions \mathcal{C} over $P = \bigcup \mathcal{S}$ *discrete solutions* or *discrete centre curves*. What makes the above problem useful is that discrete solutions approximate DTW 1-MEDIAN reasonably well:

Lemma 7. *Let $p \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, and let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be an instance of DTW 1-MEDIAN over (X, d^p) for any metric space (X, d) . Then an optimum solution for DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN on \mathcal{S} is a 2^p -approximation for DTW 1-MEDIAN on \mathcal{S} .*

Proof. Let \mathbf{c} be an optimum centre curve for \mathcal{S} . For each $x \in \mathbf{c}$, let x' be the point in S_x that is closest to x , so that $d(x, x') \leq d(x, y)$ for all $y \in S_x$. Now, let \mathbf{c}' be the curve obtained from \mathbf{c} by replacing each point x by x' , so that \mathbf{c}' is a solution to DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN on \mathcal{S} . The cost of \mathbf{c}' is at most

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{c}') &= \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}'} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x', y)^p \leq \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} (d(x', x) + d(x, y))^p \\ &\leq 2^p \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y)^p = 2^p \cdot \phi(\mathbf{c}) \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

See Figure 14 for an example.

Although Theorem 2 immediately implies that there is no constant factor approximation for DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN, we can still make use of discrete solutions when working with restrictions of DTW 1-MEDIAN.

6.2 Approximating constant length centre curves

In the case of DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN with ℓ constant, an optimum discrete solution can be found in polynomial time, essentially by a brute-force method. This immediately leads to a 2^p -approximation.

Lemma 8. *There is 2^p -approximation algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN over (X, d^p) for any metric space (X, d) and any $p \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, with a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}((mn)^{\ell+1}\ell)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be a set of curves of length m , and $P = \bigcup \mathcal{S}$ as before. There are no more than $(mn)^\ell$ sequences of length ℓ over P , so by an exhaustive search we can find in polynomial time (for constant ℓ) an optimum discrete solution \mathbf{c}' for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN on \mathcal{S} . By Lemma 7, \mathbf{c}' is the desired 2^p -approximation. Computing a DTW distance n times for each centre curve accounts for the $+1$ term in the exponent of the time complexity. \square

However, we can use the 2^p -approximation algorithm to obtain a better approximation ratio, using a technique similar to the one used in for instance [BDS20], [DPS19] and [FFK19]. Over \mathbb{R}^v , the idea is to look for curves whose vertices lie on some appropriate grid. When the grid is chosen finely enough, there will be solutions on the grid which approximate an optimum centre curve closely. Rather than working over \mathbb{R}^v , we can just as easily work over spaces with a bounded doubling dimension.

Definition 16. A metric space (X, d) has *doubling dimension* D if any ball of radius r can be covered by at most 2^D balls of radius $r/2$.

For computational purposes, we also assume that if (X, d) has doubling dimension D and given a point $x \in X$ and radius r , we can compute the centres of the 2^D balls of radius $r/2$ covering the ball of radius r centred at x , in time only depending on D .

Theorem 8. *Let (X, d) be a metric space with constant doubling dimension D , and let $p \in \mathbb{Z}_+$. For any $\epsilon > 0$, there is a $(1+\epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN over (X, d^p) , with a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}((mn/\epsilon)^{D\ell+1}\ell)$. Here, m and n are the length and number of input curves, respectively.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_X$ be an instance of DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN, and let \mathbf{c} be an optimum centre curve of cost $\phi(\mathbf{c}) = \text{OPT}$. As in the proof of Lemma 7, let \mathbf{c}' be the discrete solution resulting from \mathbf{c} by replacing each $x \in \mathbf{c}$ by the closest point x' in S_x to x . Then $\phi(\mathbf{c}') \leq 2^p \cdot \text{OPT}$, and we can find \mathbf{c}' as in Lemma 8 in polynomial time. Our strategy is to try many curves whose vertices are close to those of \mathbf{c}' , at least one of which approximates the optimum centre curve \mathbf{c} well.

Let $R = \phi(\mathbf{c}')^{1/p}$. Using a crude bound, we have that $d(x, x') \leq \text{OPT}^{1/p} \leq R$ for any $x \in \mathbf{c}$. See Figure 15 for an illustration of the situation so far.

Fix a $\delta > 0$, to be determined later. Since (X, d) has doubling dimension D , it is easy to check that we can cover the ball $B(x', R)$ centred at x' of radius R with $\mathcal{O}((R/\delta)^D)$ balls of radius δ , for any x' . For each $x' \in \mathbf{c}'$ let G_x be the set of

Figure 15: The relation between \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{c}' in the proof of Theorem 8.

centres of these $\mathcal{O}((R/\delta)^D)$ balls. Now, any point within a distance of R from some $x' \in \mathbf{c}$ is within a distance of δ from some point in G_x .

It follows that every point $x \in \mathbf{c}$ on the optimum solution is within a distance of δ from some point in G_x . Let \mathbf{c}^* be the median solution resulting from \mathbf{c} by replacing each point $x \in \mathbf{c}$ by the closest point \bar{x} in G_x . Using the triangle inequality in (X, d) , we find that

$$\phi(\mathbf{c}^*) = \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(\bar{x}, y)^p \leq \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} (d(\bar{x}, x) + d(x, y))^p \leq \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} (\delta + d(x, y))^p$$

Knowing that $\text{OPT} = \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y)^p$, we want to set δ small enough to guarantee that $\phi(\mathbf{c}^*) \leq (1 + \epsilon)\text{OPT}$. By a binomial expansion (recalling that $p \in \mathbb{Z}_+$),

$$\begin{aligned} (\delta + d(x, y))^p &= d(x, y)^p + \delta \cdot \sum_{i=1}^p \binom{p}{i} \delta^{i-1} d(x, y)^{p-i} \\ &\leq d(x, y)^p + \delta \cdot R^{p-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^p \binom{p}{i} \\ &< d(x, y)^p + \delta \cdot R^{p-1} \cdot 2^p. \end{aligned}$$

Now, setting

$$\delta = \epsilon \cdot \frac{1}{2^{2p} n(m + \ell)} \cdot R,$$

and noting that the summation $\sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x}$ has at most $n(m + \ell)$ terms, since a warping path in $\mathcal{W}_{m, \ell}$ is at most $m + \ell$ long, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{c}^*) &\leq \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} (\delta + d(x, y))^p \\ &\leq \delta \cdot R^{p-1} \cdot 2^p \cdot n(m + \ell) + \sum_{x \in \mathbf{c}} \sum_{y \in S_x} d(x, y)^p \\ &\leq \epsilon \cdot \frac{1}{2^p} R^p + \text{OPT} \\ &\leq (1 + \epsilon)\text{OPT}. \end{aligned}$$

In the last step, we used that $R^P = \phi(\mathbf{c}')$ is a 2^P -approximation for the optimum \mathbf{c} .

Finally, we can use an exhaustive search to find \mathbf{c}^* . Indeed, we simply try out all curves in $G_{x_1} \times \cdots \times G_{x_\ell}$ (where we take $\mathbf{c} = (x_1, \dots, x_\ell)$). The number of such curves is

$$\mathcal{O}(|G_x|^\ell) = \mathcal{O}\left(\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right)^{D\ell}\right) = \mathcal{O}\left(\left(\frac{nm}{\epsilon}\right)^{D\ell}\right).$$

The total resulting time complexity of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}\left(\left(\frac{mn}{\epsilon}\right)^{D\ell+1}\ell\right)$; the extra factor of $mn\ell$ comes from having to compute a DTW distance n times for each \mathbf{c}^* in order to find the cost $\phi(\mathbf{c}^*)$. Note that this complexity dominates that of computing the 2^P -approximation \mathbf{c}' . \square

The following illustration summarises the steps of the $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm:

Step 1: find an optimum discrete centre curve \mathbf{c}' .

Step 2: find a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation \mathbf{c}^* close to the optimum \mathbf{c} .

7 The DBA heuristic

As we have seen, DTW 1-MEDIAN is NP-hard, and impossible to approximate within a constant factor unless $P = NP$. Even for the restricted case of constant length centre curves, the runtime of the algorithms we have seen in Sections 5 to 6 is impractical. Naturally, the focus has historically been on algorithms without approximation guarantees, but that work well enough in practice. In this section, we discuss the heuristic which has survived the test of time the best and remains popular, known today as the DBA heuristic. The simple algorithm is based on some of the ideas we have already seen in Section 5.

The average curve problem has a rich history of heuristics, starting with the speech recognition community in the 1970s. One of the first serious attempt at tackling DTW 1-MEDIAN was put forward in [RW79], and was based on an iterative local optimisation procedure, reminiscent of Lloyd’s (k -means) algorithm for k -MEDIAN. A limited form of this heuristic was rediscovered in [ACS03], and based on this work, the original method (from [RW79]) was recovered in [HNF08]. Most recently, Petitjean, Ketterlin and Gançarski rediscovered and popularised the same heuristic under the name of *DTW Barycentric Average (DBA)* [PKG11]. Its combination of simplicity and effectiveness is hard to beat, and it is the basis for most recent improved heuristics (for example [SJ18; Mor+18; LZZ19; JFS19]).

In parallel, there was a significant development of hierarchical clustering techniques for the average curve problem. A popular heuristic called NLAAF was introduced in [Gup+96] and later refined in [NR09] under the name PSA. These algorithms leverage the fact that we can compute the average of *two* curves quite well, and simply combine input curves pairwise until a single average curve remains. In practice, however, this strategy turns out to be inferior to the DBA heuristic and its improvements, and has largely become obsolete.

See [SJ18] for a more in-depth review of different strategies for average curve heuristics, and [Bri+19] for an empirical comparison of various state-of-the-art heuristics.

The DBA heuristic is essentially inspired by the structure of the optimum centre curves as by Proposition 2: for an optimum centre curve \mathbf{c} , each $x \in \mathbf{c}$ is the 1-median of the points S_x on the input curves. For the heuristic, we can simply compute S_x for each point x on a candidate centre curve, and *set* x to be an optimum 1-median of S_x . This may then be iterated. Without further ado, see the full Algorithm 1.

The two important steps that are iterated, are highlighted with line numbers: first computing S_x for each point x on the candidate curve \mathbf{c}' , and then using an algorithm for 1-MEDIAN in X to reset the points x . See Figure 16 for an illustration of the two steps, and Figure 17 for an example of two full iterations

Algorithm 1: The DTW Barycentric Average (DBA) heuristic

Input: A set of curves $\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{V}_X$, a candidate centre curve $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ of length ℓ , and an algorithm A to compute optimum 1-medians of subsets of X .

Output: A centre curve $\mathbf{c}' \in \mathcal{V}_X$ of length ℓ .

```
c'  $\leftarrow$  c
do
  1  $\phi_{\text{old}} \leftarrow \phi(\mathbf{c}')$ 
    Compute  $S_x$  for all  $x \in \mathbf{c}'$ 
    for  $x \in \mathbf{c}'$  do
  2   |  $x \leftarrow A(S_x)$ 
    end
while  $\phi(\mathbf{c}') < \phi_{\text{old}}$ 
return c'
```

Figure 16: The two main steps involved in the DBA heuristic.

of the algorithm.

Algorithm 1 works for candidates \mathbf{c} of any length, so that it may be used for both DTW 1-MEDIAN and DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN. Note also that (X, d) is not required to be a metric space (as with the dynamic program in Theorem 7); we only need to be able to compute optimum 1-medians in X . This means the heuristic also works with respect to the squared Euclidean distance, for example.

We have written the algorithm in a form close to how one would implement it. However, in the language of Section 5.1, we could say that the DBA heuristic simply iterates

$$\mathbf{c} \leftarrow \mathbf{c}_{1\text{-med}}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{c})).$$

We have seen (Lemma 2) that optimum centre curves are stable under this iteration. However, there are many other non-optimum curves which are stable under this iteration too, and which the DBA heuristic may get stuck on.

Figure 17: An example of the DBA heuristic with two iterations. Each row shows one iteration.

One question which immediately presents itself is whether the DBA heuristic always terminates, and if yes, in how many iterations. We can answer the first question positively: since the objective function is strictly decreased in each iteration but the algorithm works with a finite search space (namely, curves of length ℓ whose points are optimum 1-medians of sections of \mathcal{S}), the algorithm must terminate after a finite number of iterations. This was also noted in [SJ18]. However, this observation gives an exponential upper bound on the possible number of iterations: it is an open question whether Algorithm 1 terminates in a polynomial number of iterations. In practice, a maximum number of iterations is often specified, or a threshold $\epsilon > 0$ such that the iteration only continues if $\phi_{\text{old}} - \phi(\mathbf{c}') > \epsilon$.

A second important question is how to select the initial candidate centre curve \mathbf{c} . One possibility is to choose some random curve from \mathcal{S} ; a more accurate guess is to take the optimum 1-medoid from \mathcal{S} , that is, $\mathbf{c} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \phi(\mathbf{s})$. If this is computationally infeasible, we could instead take a 1-medoid from a random subset of \mathcal{S} . In principle, the DBA heuristic can be combined with any other heuristic for DTW 1-MEDIAN as a kind of local post-processing optimisation.

7.1 Performance of DBA

In [Bri+19], a comparison is made between the DBA heuristic and exact solutions on the UCR dataset [Dau+18], where we have $X = \mathbb{R}$ with the squared Euclidean distance. It shows, for example, that on the tested dataset, the DBA heuristic yields a 5/4-approximation with a probability of about 0.6, and a 3/2-approximation with a probability of about 0.9.

By Theorem 2, we know that the DBA heuristic does not has a constant ap-

Figure 18: Illustration of how the DBA heuristic can fail. On the left, an optimum centre curve. On the right, the result of the DBA heuristic initialised with one of the input curves.

proximation ratio (and neither does any other heuristic for DTW 1-MEDIAN). However, there are even simpler examples showing that the DBA heuristic in particular does not have a constant approximation ratio.

Example 13. Let us take $X = \mathbb{R}$ with the squared Euclidean distance, and take \mathcal{S} to be a set containing $n - 1$ copies of the curve $(0, 1, -1)$ and one copy of the curve $(0, -1, -1)$. Suppose we take $\mathbf{c} = (0, -1, -1)$ as the initial 1-median candidate. Then we can check that the DBA heuristic terminates after one iteration with a curve of cost $(n^2 - n) / (2n - 1)$, while an optimum solution has cost $(n - 1) / n$. Thus, the approximation ratio of DBA for this input tends to $n/2$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

See Figure 18 for some intuition of how the DBA heuristic might fail. On the left side, an optimum 1-median is shown. On the right hand, we see one possible output of the DBA heuristic, with one of the input curves as initial candidate. This output is slightly more than twice as expansive (under the squared Euclidean distance) as the optimum 1-median on the left. The problem is that although the DBA output is locally optimal, it fails on a global level.

If we choose an initial candidate outside of \mathcal{S} , then the heuristic can be even worse. The simple example $\mathcal{S} = \{(0, 1, -1)\}$ and $\mathbf{c} = (0, -1, -1)$ shows that the approximation ratio can be unbounded since the DBA heuristic might converge on a non-zero cost solution when the optimum solution has zero cost.

8 Conclusion

Through exploring the DTW 1-MEDIAN problem, we have seen both structure in its solutions, but also its inherent difficulty. On one side, both the discrete and geometric structure of optimum centre curves are highlighted in Section 5, and finding constant length centre curves has been shown to be possible in polynomial time. On the other hand, the difficulty of the average curve problem has been strengthened relative to previous results by showing that there are no constant factor approximation algorithms.

However, we are left with a number of open questions, some of which we mention here.

Question 1. *Is there an approximation algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN with an approximation ratio depending on n ?*

Since the DTW distance satisfies the m -relaxed triangle inequality, a 1-medoid is a $2m$ -approximation for DTW 1-MEDIAN. On the other hand, we know by Theorem 2 that we cannot approximate DTW 1-MEDIAN better than within a factor of $(\log n)^\delta$ for some δ . However, it is an open question whether there is an approximation algorithm with an approximation ratio of n or even n^δ for some δ .

Question 2. *Are there exact algorithms for DTW 1-MEDIAN with better runtimes?*

It has already been asked in [BFN19] whether there is any exact algorithm for DTW 1-MEDIAN with a runtime of $\mathcal{O}(m^{\alpha n})$ for some small $\alpha > 1$, or even just $\mathcal{O}(m^n)$. In light of Theorem 1, this would essentially be the best possible runtime depending exponentially on n . Meanwhile, there is also an exact algorithm for centre curves of constant length ℓ , but since it makes use of Cylindrical Algebraic Decomposition (CAD), the dependency on ℓ is doubly exponential. A natural question is whether there is any exact algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN running in $\mathcal{O}((mn)^{\text{poly}(\ell)})$. The corresponding question for DTW 1-MEDIAN is whether there is any algorithm with a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^{\text{poly}(m)})$, or even $\mathcal{O}(n^{\alpha m})$ for some constant α .

Question 3. *Are there randomised algorithms for DTW 1-MEDIAN with a good expected performance?*

For some optimisation problems, there are randomised algorithms which produce good expected approximations even if no absolute guarantees can be proven. It would be interesting to analyse the expected performance of heuristics such as the DBA algorithm, initialised in some random way. Even though we have shown that the DTW 1-MEDIAN is hard to approximate, algorithms with a good expected performance may exist and could be useful in practice.

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A The k -MEDIAN problem

In this section, we give a succinct overview over the k -MEDIAN problem. Of most importance to the main text is the last part, about the 1-MEDIAN problem. However, this entire section serves to provide context to the DTW k -MEDIAN problem. After introducing the general k -MEDIAN problem, we discuss some of the most important versions together with hardness and approximation results.

There are many variants of the k -MEDIAN problem, depending on the space and distance we are working with. One of the most common and intuitive versions is simply over Euclidean space:

EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN

Instance: A set of points $\mathcal{S} = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}^p$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Task: Find a set of k centres $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, \dots, c_k\} \subset \mathbb{R}^p$ that minimises the cost

$$\sum_{x \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} |x - c|,$$

where $|x - c|$ is the Euclidean distance between x and c .

See Figure 19 for an example. Note that a median of a set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathbb{R}$ as we know it from statistics is indeed an optimum solution to the EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN problem on \mathcal{S} in the above sense, motivating the name of the k -MEDIAN problem.

We may want to work over more general spaces than \mathbb{R}^p and with more general distance functions than the Euclidean distance. In the following, let Δ be a set, and $D: \Delta \times \Delta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ be a distance function (so D is symmetric and satisfies $D(x, x) = 0$ for all $x \in \Delta$).

k -MEDIAN

Instance: A set $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \Delta$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Task: Find a set of k centres $\mathcal{C} \subseteq \Delta$ that minimise the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} D(x, c).$$

If there is a chance of ambiguity, we can write $\phi_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathcal{C})$ to denote the cost function.

Figure 19: An instance of EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN in \mathbb{R}^2 , with 4 centres \mathcal{C} shown as large red dots. The cost is the sum of the lengths of the dotted lines.

Of course, EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN is a special case since we can take $\Delta = \mathbb{R}^D$ and D to be the Euclidean metric. The above formulation also includes the popular variation where $\Delta = \mathbb{R}^D$ but D is the squared Euclidean distance. Note that the squared Euclidean distance does not satisfy the triangle inequality: we do not require D to be a metric.

In general, k -MEDIAN may not be well-defined for some (Δ, D) , because optimum solutions may not exist in some cases when Δ is infinite. Therefore, we always study k -MEDIAN for specific cases of (Δ, D) .

An important case is when Δ is finite: in this case, Δ is usually regarded as part of the input. The resulting problem is popular in the context of the combinatorial optimisation for its similarity with FACILITY LOCATION:

DISCRETE k -MEDIAN

Instance: Sets Δ and $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \Delta$, a distance function D on Δ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Task: Find a set of k centres $\mathcal{C} \subseteq \Delta$ that minimises the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} D(x, c).$$

Often, the above problem is simply used with $\mathcal{S} = \Delta$. The following closely related generalisation is also commonly encountered:

RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN

Instance: Sets \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{F} , a distance function D on $\mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{F}$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Task: Find a set of k centres $\mathcal{C} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ that minimises the cost

$$\phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{S}} \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} D(x, c).$$

This variation can be seen as a special version of k -FACILITY LOCATION, where \mathcal{F} is the set of facilities, but the cost of opening any facility is 0. In the literature, the distance D is almost always required to be metric.

Note that there does not seem to be a consensus in the literature on what to call the above problems, and all of them are often just called the “ k -median” problem. For example, [LS16; Byr+17] call RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN the “ k -median” problem, [ABS10] calls k -MEDIAN the “generalised k -median” problem, [Cha+02; JMS02] call DISCRETE k -MEDIAN the “ k -median” problem and [KSS05] calls EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN the “ k -median clustering” problem; the list goes on. In order to give a precise overview, we have to use some non-standard names such as RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN.

A.1 Hardness of k -MEDIAN

In Section 4 we have seen that DTW 1-MEDIAN is NP-hard (and even hard to approximate within a constant factor). In contrast, many variations of k -MEDIAN

can be solved in polynomial time when k is constant. For example, DISCRETE k -MEDIAN can be solved exactly by trying all $\mathcal{O}(n^k)$ sets of k centres from the $|\Delta| = n$ input points. This is why, for these problems, the parameter k is considered part of the input. Then n^k is not polynomial in the size of the instance, and in fact it turns out that the problem is NP-hard.

A.1.1 Discrete k -MEDIAN problems

Commonly studied k -MEDIAN problems over discrete spaces (where Δ is part of the input), such as DISCRETE k -MEDIAN and its generalisation RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN, are all NP-hard. In fact, these problems are even hard to approximate within a certain constant factor. In the case of RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN, we have the following:

Lemma 9 ([JMS02]). *For RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN where D is metric, there does not exist any approximation algorithm with an approximation ratio strictly better than $1 + 2/e$ unless $P = NP$.*

Perhaps unsurprisingly, the problem becomes impossible to approximate when we do not require D to be metric; this also holds for the special case of DISCRETE k -MEDIAN:

Lemma 10. *There does not exist any approximation algorithm for (non-metric) DISCRETE k -MEDIAN unless $P = NP$.*

The proof is simple and instructive enough to include here: it uses a simple reduction from the following classical NP-hard decision problem.

DOMINATING SET

Instance: A graph $G = (V, E)$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Task: Does there exist a dominating set of size k in G , that is, a set of k vertices $S \subseteq V$ such that each vertex in G is either included in S or is adjacent to some element of S ?

Proof of Lemma 10. Suppose that there exists a polynomial time α -approximation algorithm for DISCRETE k -MEDIAN, where α may be constant or some polynomial function of instance size. Let $G = (V, E)$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ be an instance of DOMINATING SET; we use the α -approximation algorithm for DISCRETE k -MEDIAN to decide whether G has a dominating set of size k . For $v, w \in V$, define $D(v, w) = 1$ when $\{v, w\} \in E$ and $D(v, w) = \alpha \cdot |E| + 1$ otherwise. Now consider the instance $\mathcal{J} = (V(G), V(G), D, k)$ of DISCRETE k -MEDIAN. If G has a dominating set of size k , then there is a solution to \mathcal{J} of cost at most $|E|$. If G does *not* have a dominating set of size k , then any solution to \mathcal{J} costs at least $\alpha \cdot |E| + 1$. Therefore, we can solve DOMINATING SET with an α -approximation to DISCRETE k -MEDIAN in polynomial time, which implies that $P = NP$. \square

A.1.2 Continuous k-MEDIAN problems

In the case of the EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN problem, we run into computational problems involving the impossibility of computing roots of general polynomials, even in the case of $k = 1$.

Lemma 11 ([Baj86]). *For $n \geq 5$ input points, the solution to the EUCLIDEAN 1-MEDIAN problem is in general the root of an irreducible polynomial of high degree, which is not solvable by radicals over \mathbb{Q} .*

This means that exact solutions to EUCLIDEAN 1-MEDIAN cannot be computed in a standard computational model.

The situation is considerably simpler for EUCLIDEAN 1-MEDIAN with the squared Euclidean distance; this is called the EUCLIDEAN 1-MEAN problem. The Euclidean 1-mean of a set of points $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ is just the average of S , in the sense that we average in each dimension. This can of course be computed exactly in polynomial time.

However, EUCLIDEAN k -MEAN is still NP-hard. In fact, even EUCLIDEAN 2-MEAN is NP-hard if we allow an arbitrary dimension [Alo+09], while the general EUCLIDEAN k -MEAN is NP-hard even over \mathbb{R}^2 [MNV09].

A.2 Algorithms for k-MEDIAN

On the discrete side, we have seen that (metric) RESTRICTED CENTRE k -MEDIAN is hard to approximate within a factor of $1 + 2/e \approx 1.736$. However, many constant factor approximation algorithms have been proposed throughout the years, culminating with a $(2.675 + \epsilon)$ -approximation [Byr+17].

For the EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN problem we can do much better, owing to the additional structure of \mathbb{R}^{ν} over general metric spaces. The first Polynomial Time Approximation Scheme (PTAS) for EUCLIDEAN k -MEDIAN over \mathbb{R}^2 was given in 1999 [ARR99]: a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm running in polynomial time for each fixed $\epsilon > 0$. After much development, the current best PTAS is given in [FMS07], and runs in $\mathcal{O}(n\nu k + \nu(k/\epsilon)^{\mathcal{O}(1)} + 2^{\mathcal{O}(k/\epsilon)})$ time.

A.2.1 The 1-MEDIAN problem

In algorithms for DTW 1-MEDIAN over X , we often need to compute 1-medians over X . Therefore, the 1-MEDIAN problem deserves special attention. Of course, the DTW 1-MEDIAN problem is itself a special case of the 1-MEDIAN problem (over the space $(\mathcal{V}_X, \text{DTW})$), but here we focus on the 1-MEDIAN problem over the underlying space X . By far the most relevant is $X = \mathbb{R}^{\nu}$.

In the two most common cases for X , we can easily find optimum 1-medians.

- (a) $X = \mathbb{R}$. Then optimum 1-medians are medians in the statistical sense. Note that this is an easy example of a space where optimum 1-medians exist, but are usually not unique.
- (b) $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the squared Euclidean distance. Here, the optimum 1-median of a finite set $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^\nu$ is the *average* of S , coordinate-wise if $\nu > 1$. This can be seen by a simple argument: the objective function is a second degree polynomial, reaching its unique minimum when its derivative is zero, and this point turns is the average.

However, even in the case of $X = \mathbb{R}^\nu$ with the (non-squared) Euclidean distance, when solutions to EUCLIDEAN 1-MEDIAN cannot be computed exactly (see Appendix A.1.2), the problem can be well approximated. In particular, the current best PTAS for EUCLIDEAN 1-MEDIAN runs in $\mathcal{O}(n\nu \log^3(n/\epsilon))$ time [Coh+16]. Since the objective function is convex, iteration methods are also effective in practice.

Of course, 1-MEDIAN problem over discrete spaces, such as DISCRETE 1-MEDIAN and RESTRICTED CENTRE 1-MEDIAN, can be solved by checking all points, and take quadratic time to solve.

In conclusion, we can safely assume that we can either compute optimum 1-medians exactly or approximate them to any desired accuracy over any space X that we consider in this paper.

B Complexity theory

Although we assume familiarity with basic complexity theory throughout this paper, we briefly define optimisation problems, approximation algorithms, parametrised complexity and the Exponential Time Hypothesis. We do not cover all formal details; for more in-depth references, see for example [GJ79] for NP-completeness, [KV18] for combinatorial optimisation problems and approximation algorithms, and [Nie06] for parametrised complexity.

First of all, the kind of problems considered in this paper (k -MEDIAN, DTW (k, ℓ) -MEDIAN) deserve a formal definition.

Definition 17. An *optimisation problem* Π consists of

- A set of *valid instances* D_Π .
- For each instance $I \in D_\Pi$, a set of *feasible solutions* S_I for I . Each $s \in S_I$ must have a size polynomial in $|I|$.
- An *objective function* ϕ_Π , computable in polynomial time, assigning to each pair (I, s) of instance and feasible solution a non-negative rational number.
- A specification of whether Π is a *minimisation* or a *maximisation* problem.

An *optimum solution* for instance I is a feasible solution $s \in S_I$ attaining the smallest, respectively largest possible objective function value for I , in case of minimisation, respectively maximisation problems. We denote by $\text{OPT}(I)$ the objective function value of an optimum solution for I .

For every optimisation problem Π , there is the corresponding decision problem which asks for each instance $I \in D_\Pi$ and constant k whether there is a feasible solution s such that $\phi_\Pi(I, s) \leq k$ or $\phi_\Pi(I, s) \geq k$ for minimisation and maximisation problems, respectively. We say that Π is *NP-hard* if the corresponding decision problem is NP-hard. For example, k -MEDIAN is NP-hard over most spaces X .

We are interested in algorithms for optimisation problems. An *exact algorithm* A for problem Π computes for each instance $I \in D_\Pi$ an optimum solution. Clearly, if there is a polynomial time exact algorithm for Π , then Π is not NP-hard. Sometimes, exponential time exact algorithms are also interesting.

Still, we want useful polynomial time algorithms even for NP-hard optimisation problems. Given that we cannot find optimum solutions for these problems in polynomial time, we could instead look for solutions that are only close to optimum in some sense. This leads to the notion of *approximation algorithms*.

Definition 18. An *approximation algorithm* A with *approximation ratio* of α (also called a α -approximation algorithm) for an optimisation problem Π is an

algorithm which computes for each instance $I \in D_\Pi$ a feasible solution $s \in S_I$ satisfying

$$\frac{1}{\alpha(|I|)} \cdot \text{OPT}(I) \leq \phi_\Pi(s) \leq \alpha(|I|) \cdot \text{OPT}(I).$$

Of particular interest are *constant factor approximation algorithms*, where the approximation ratio $\alpha(|I|)$ is constant. Of course, if $\alpha = 1$ then we have an exact algorithm: the closer α is to 1 the better the approximation algorithm. For example, Lemma 8 gives a 2-approximation algorithm for DTW $(1, \ell)$ -MEDIAN over \mathbb{R} with constant ℓ .

Sometimes, we can still compute optimum solutions to NP-hard optimisation problem somewhat efficiently by isolating computational complexity to a specific parameter of the problem.

Definition 19. A *parametrised optimisation problem* is an optimisation problem where the instances are pairs (I, k) with $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $n = |(I, k)|$ denote the size of an instance. A parametrised problem Π is *slice-wise polynomial* if there is an exact algorithm for Π with a runtime in $\mathcal{O}(n^{f(k)})$ for some computable function f . Furthermore, Π is called *fixed-parameter tractable* if there is an exact algorithm for Π with a runtime bounded by $f(k) \cdot n^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ for some computable function f .

The class of slice-wise polynomial problems is denoted XP, while the class of all fixed-parameter tractable problems is called FPT. VERTEX COVER is maybe the most archetypical fixed-parameter tractable problem (the parameter being the size of the vertex cover). Of course, the appeal of fixed-parameter tractability is that we can compute vertex covers of constant size (if they exist) in polynomial time, even if the general VERTEX COVER problem is NP-hard.

In the same way that NP-hard problems are presumably not solvable in polynomial time, there is a notion of hardness for parametrised problems which we can use as evidence that some problems are *not* fixed-parameter tractable. Although we refer to for instance [Nie06] for the somewhat involved formal definitions, the relevant complexity class is called W[1] (an analogue of NP). We can define reductions between parametrised problems, and hence the notion of W[1]-hardness, and it is widely believed that $W[1] \neq \text{FPT}$ (an analogue of $P \neq \text{NP}$). In other words, if it is shown via a reduction that some problem is W[1]-hard, then we presume that it *cannot* be solved in $f(k) \cdot n^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ time. W[1]-hard problems are also called fixed-parameter *intractable*. A classical example of a fixed-parameter intractable problem is INDEPENDENT SET, while we have seen in Section 4 that DTW 1-MEDIAN is fixed-parameter intractable.

Lastly, we look at the *Exponential Time Hypothesis (ETH)*, a frequently used conjecture in complexity theory which enables a more fine-grained analysis of the lowest possible runtime of algorithms for many optimisation problems.

Conjecture (Exponential Time Hypothesis). *Let s be the infimum of all $\delta > 0$ for which 3-SAT can be solved in $\mathcal{O}(2^{\delta n})$ time. Then $s > 0$.*

Essentially, the ETH postulates that 3-SAT cannot be solved in sub-exponential time. The ETH directly implies, among others, that $P \neq NP$ and that $W[1] \neq FPT$. Still, the ETH is widely assumed to be true.

C Linear programming

For many discrete optimisation problems, linear programming is an indispensable tool for either exact or approximation algorithms. For example, linear programming techniques have been central in most approximation algorithms for the FACILITY LOCATION problem (see for instance [Li11]), a problem closely related to k -MEDIAN. In our case, DTW k -MEDIAN and even DTW 1-MEDIAN are unwieldy to formulate as (linear) programs over arbitrary metric spaces (X, d) because we would have to encode 1-medians of sections of \mathcal{S} . However, we *can* write DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN as a relatively simple integer linear program. Here, we take advantage of the fact that solutions to DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN are easy to represent: they are just a sequence of points from the input curves. By Lemma 7, an optimum discrete centre curve is a 2-approximation for an optimum (non-discrete) centre curve.

Although we have not found any immediate uses for the linear programming formulation of DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN, we include it here because it gives a new and interesting perspective on the DTW distance and the average curve problem.

In a recent and unrelated work, Froese and Hansknecht worked on solving DTW 1-MEDIAN exactly using mixed-integer quadratic programming [FH19]. They used a different formulation, which is of independent interest.

C.1 The DTW distance as a linear program

As a warm-up, we consider the problem of writing the DTW distance between two curves \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} as a linear problem. Although there are different ways forward, the easiest is to work directly with warping paths as integer lattice paths.

Define the directed integer lattice graph $G_{\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b}}$ with vertex set $V = \{1, \dots, m\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$ and all possible directed edges that jump with steps $(0, 1)$, $(1, 1)$ or $(1, 0)$. Let the cost c of incoming edges incident to (i, j) be $d(a_i, b_j)$, and also add a cost of $d(a_1, b_1)$ to outgoing edges incident to $(1, 1)$. We make $G_{\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b}}$ into the instance of a min-cost flow problem by defining $(1, 1)$ to be a source and (m, m) to be a sink of value 1. Then the “fractional” DTW distance between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is

$$\min\{c(f) \mid f \text{ is a flow in } G_{\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b}}\}.$$

Since all the constraints to this flow problem are integral, the LP always has an integral optimum solution: the DTW distance between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} .

See Figure 20 for an example.

Figure 20: An example of the LP-formulation of the DTW distance. A minimum cost flow in $G_{a,b}$ corresponding to an optimum warping path between the curves on the right is shown. The costs of the three edges in the min-cost flow are $d_1 + d_2$, d_3 and d_4 respectively.

C.2 DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN as a linear program

When writing DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN as a linear program, we first have to consider how to represent solutions. The discrete nature of the problem makes this easier: integral solutions are just sequences of m points from the input curves. In a linear program, we get a notion of “fractional” curve.

Consider an instance of DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN: a set \mathcal{S} of n curves of length m over a metric space (X, d) . Let $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_M\} = \bigcup \mathcal{S}$ be the set of points of the sequences in \mathcal{S} ; note that $M = |P| \leq mn$. To define a fractional curve \mathbf{x} over P , let $0 \leq x_{ia} \leq 1$ indicate the fraction of the i th point of \mathbf{x} that is at p_a , for $1 \leq i \leq m$ and $1 \leq a \leq M$. Each point of \mathbf{x} needs a total weight of 1, so we set $\sum_{a=1}^M x_{ia} = 1$ for all i . As desired, integral \mathbf{x} (with $x_{ia} \in \{0, 1\}$) correspond to a sequence of points from P of length m . See Figure 21 for an example of a fractional curve \mathbf{x} .

Now, we need a way of writing the DTW distance between \mathbf{x} and curves in \mathcal{S} as a linear program. We can do this analogously to how we computed the DTW

Figure 21: An example of a fractional curve. The region drawn for each x_i corresponds to the points p_a for which $x_{ia} > 0$, and the fractions drawn in the regions are the values x_{ia} .

Figure 22: An example of a fractional solution to DTW 1-MEDIAN.

distance between two regular curves using min-cost flows.

Define the graph $G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{b}}$ with vertex set $V = \{1, \dots, M\} \times \{1, \dots, m\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$ and with all possible directed edges that make the steps $(a, 0, 1)$, $(a, 1, 0)$ and $(a, 1, 1)$ for any a . Equivalently, we can also define $G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{b}}$ as the tensor product $G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{b}} = K_M \times G_{(1, \dots, m), \mathbf{b}}$, where K_M is the complete graph with M vertices.

We define edge costs c similarly to in $G_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}$. Let the cost of all edges into (a, i, j) be $d(p_a, b_j)$, and add a cost of $d(p_a, b_1)$ to all outgoing edges from $(a, 1, 1)$.

Some flow constraints are needed to make $G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{b}}$ the desired min-cost flow problem instance. For all $1 \leq a \leq M$, let $(a, 1, 1)$ be a source with x_{1a} units of out-flow, and let (a, m, m) be a sink with x_{ma} units of the in-flow. Let the total capacity of the set of all edges going into the vertices $\{(a, i, j) \mid 1 \leq j \leq m\}$ be x_{ia} . Now we can write the fractional DTW distance between x and \mathbf{b} as the following integer LP:

$$\min\{c(f) \mid f \text{ is a flow in } G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{b}}\}.$$

At this point, we can formulate the relaxation of DISCRETE DTW 1-MEDIAN as a linear program.

$$\min \left\{ \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} c(f_{\mathbf{s}}) \mid f_{\mathbf{s}} \text{ is a flow in } G_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{s}}, 0 \leq x_{ia} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

See Figure 22 for an example of what a solution to this LP can look like. Note that as the following example shows, the above LP does not have a bounded integrality ratio.

Example 14. Consider the input curves $(0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0)$ and $(0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0)$. The fractional centre curve $\frac{1}{2}(0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) + \frac{1}{2}(0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0)$ has cost 0, but there is no integral centre curve of cost 0.

D Additional variations of the DTW distance

Some additional variations of the DTW distance are worth mentioning. Though these variations are not particularly relevant to the rest of this paper, they are of independent interest and give additional perspectives on the DTW distance.

D.1 The time-warp-invariant distance

Jain proposes in [Jai19] a way to resolve the DTW distance’s violation of the identity of indiscernibles.

First, it is shown that the relation $\mathbf{a} \sim \mathbf{b} \iff \text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$ is an equivalence relation. This is not self-evident since the DTW distance does not satisfy the triangle inequality: it could have been conceivable that there are curves $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{V}_X$ with $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \text{DTW}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) = 0$ but with $\text{DTW}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) > 0$. (Indeed, this may be the case for example the w -DTW distance, as seen in Section 2.4.)

Since \sim is an equivalence relation, we can consider the quotient space \mathcal{V}_X/\sim , and with a bit of care we can let DTW induce a new distance function in the quotient space. This induced distance function is called the *time-warp-invariant* (*twi*) distance in [Jai19], and can in turn be mapped back to the whole space \mathcal{V}_X . The resulting distance function satisfies the identity of indiscernibles, but is still not metric. In effect, $\text{twi}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ is the DTW distance between the curves resulting from \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} by compressing all runs of the same element to a single element. For example, $\text{twi}((0, 0, 2, 1), (2, 2, 2, 1, 1)) = \text{DTW}((0, 2, 1), (2, 1)) = 2$ even though $\text{DTW}((0, 0, 2, 1), (2, 2, 2, 1, 1)) = 4$.

The main advantage of the time-warp-invariant distance highlighted in [Jai19] is that it is invariant (almost by definition) under the compression of runs of repeated elements in time series. Eliminating runs of repeated elements can drastically speed up processing, depending on the data. This could be especially effective in combination with discretising the underlying space, so that similar values are considered identical and can be compressed.

D.2 Continuous dynamic time warping distance

Readers familiar with the Fréchet distance will know that there are two variations of the Fréchet distance: the discrete and the continuous versions. In Section 2.3, we introduced the discrete Fréchet distance, and highlighted its similarity with the DTW distance. A natural question is thus if there is some “continuous DTW distance”, similar to the continuous Fréchet distance. First, of course, we have to define the continuous Fréchet distance.

Definition 20. Let the continuous functions $\alpha, \beta : [0, 1] \rightarrow X$ parametrise two curves in the metric space (X, d) . The *continuous Fréchet distance* between α

and β is defined as

$$d_F(\alpha, \beta) = \inf_{\substack{f: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1] \\ g: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]}} \sup_{t \in [0,1]} d(\alpha(f(t)), \beta(g(t))),$$

where the infimum is taken over all continuous increasing functions f, g .

Already in one of the first independent works on the DTW distance [VZ70], a continuous DTW distance was mentioned. By 2005–2007, a notion of continuous DTW distance was rediscovered and further developed independently in [Bra+05] and [EFV07]. In her PhD thesis, Buchin [Buc07] dedicates a chapter to a number of variations of a continuous DTW distance. The more recent publications use the name *summed Fréchet distance*.

Essentially, the idea is to replace the supremum by an integral, analogously to how the DTW distance is obtained from the discrete Fréchet distance by replacing a maximum by a summation. However, there are a few different ways to define the resulting integral. One way is the following, referred to as δ_α in [Buc07]:

Definition 21. Let the continuous functions $\alpha, \beta : [0, 1] \rightarrow X$ parametrise two curves in the metric space (X, d) . The *continuous DTW distance* between α and β is defined as the path integral

$$\text{CDTW}(\alpha, \beta) = \inf_{\substack{f: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1] \\ g: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]}} \int_0^1 d(\alpha(f(t)), \beta(g(t))) \sqrt{f'(t)^2 + g'(t)^2} dt,$$

where the infimum is taken over all piecewise continuously differentiable, increasing functions f, g . The square root term in the integral is the length of the path element.

In the literature, it is also common to “average” the above distance by dividing by the length of the path we integrate over.

No algorithm is known to compute the continuous DTW distance exactly. It seems to be an open question whether the problem is NP-hard. However, there is a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -approximation algorithm to compute the continuous DTW distance for polygonal curves [MSS18].

Just like the DTW distance, Buchin shows that neither the above definition, nor any other natural definition of a continuous DTW distance that she considered, satisfies the triangle inequality. In fact, the above definition does not even satisfy any δ -relaxed triangle inequality.

In conclusion, although a continuous DTW distance is an interesting idea, at the moment it appears too difficult to work with to be of any great significance.